

TITAN

Trusted environments for confidential AI computing
and secure data sharing

D1.2 Technical requirements for EOSC secure data sharing and processing

07/11/2024

Title	D1.2 - Technical requirements for EOSC secure data sharing and processing
Document description	This deliverable D1.2 explains the requirements elicitation process by summarising, prioritising, and explaining the TITAN technical requirements for EOSC secure sharing and processing. In addition, the document outlines TITAN's objectives, and the relation to the requirements. An annotated preliminary requirements list serves as a base for the further implementation of the TITAN infrastructure.
Deliverable Type	R: Report
Dissemination level	PUB: public
Status	F: final
Task	T1.2, T1.3
Lead Partner	FRA
Partners Involved	UKO, UMU, FUJ, SAR, ITA, VEN, UVC, CAB, UEF, ZEN, CHA, INS, ODY
Date	M9

Revision history	Author	Delivery date	Summary of changes and comments
Version 01	Eduard Wolf (FRA), Volker Riediger (UKO), Julian Flake (UKO), Veronika Vasileva (UKO)	29/08/2024	Initial draft
Version 02	Eduard Wolf (FRA) Volker Riediger (UKO), Julian Flake (UKO), Veronika Vasileva (UKO)	07/10/2024	Updated draft
Version 03	Eduard Wolf (FRA), Volker Riediger (UKO), Julian Flake (UKO), Veronika Vasileva (UKO)	29/10/2024	Prefinal version
Version 04	Nenad Gligoric (ZEN), Nikolka Tomic (TRI)	05/11/2024	Document Review
Final Version	Eduard Wolf (FRA), Volker Riediger (UKO), Julian Flake (UKO), Veronika Vasileva (UKO)	07/11/2024	Final version

DISCLAIMER

Funded by the European Union under the GA No 101129822. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European Research Executive Agency (REA). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

A software platform solution for confidential data collaboration
& secure and privacy-preserving data processing

Grant Agreement No: 101129822
Call: HORIZON-INFRA-2023-EOSC-01
Topic: HORIZON-INFRA-2023-EOSC-01-06
Type of action: HORIZON Research and Innovation Actions

COPYRIGHT NOTICE

© TITAN Consortium, 2024

This deliverable contains original unpublished work except where clearly indicated otherwise. Acknowledgement of previously published material and of the work of others has been made through appropriate citation, quotation, or both. Reproduction is authorised provided the source is acknowledged.

Table of Contents

LIST OF FIGURES	4
LIST OF TABLES	5
LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS AND ACRONYMS	6
1 EXECUTIVE SUMMARY	8
2 INTRODUCTION	9
3 PROJECT SUMMARY	10
3.1. THE TITAN PROJECT	10
3.2. OBJECTIVES	10
4 EUROPEAN DATA SPACE INITIATIVES	12
4.1. INTRODUCTION TO DATA SPACES	12
4.2. GAIA-X.....	13
4.3. INTERNATIONAL DATA SPACES ASSOCIATIONS (IDSA).....	14
4.4. DATA SPACES SUPPORT CENTRE (DSSC)	15
4.5. IMPORTANCE OF DATA SPACES FOR TITAN	15
5 TECHNICAL REQUIREMENTS ELICITATION AND ANALYSIS	17
5.1. INTRODUCTION	17
5.2. METHODOLOGY	19
5.3. USE CASES	19
5.3.1. <i>Use Case 1: Confidential sharing and collaboration with sensitive agrifood government data</i>	20
5.3.2. <i>Use Case 2: Collaborative Use of ML in Healthcare</i>	24
5.4. EOSC INTEROPERABILITY FRAMEWORK.....	27
5.5. PREPARATION	30
5.5.1. <i>Elicitation Criteria</i>	30
5.5.2. <i>Requirement Templates</i>	32
5.5.3. <i>Rules for TITAN requirements elicitation</i>	36
5.6. LEGAL AND TECHNICAL REQUIREMENTS COLLECTION	40
5.7. LEGAL AND TECHNICAL REQUIREMENTS ELICITATION AND ANALYSIS	40
5.8. PRELIMINARY TITAN SOFTWARE ARCHITECTURE	41
5.8.1. <i>Assets summary</i>	41
5.8.2. <i>General Architecture</i>	47
5.8.3. <i>Architecture flow</i>	48
6 RESULTS AND CONCLUSION	50
7 REQUIREMENTS LIST	50
REFERENCES	51
APPENDIX	53
TECHNICAL REQUIREMENTS.....	53
<i>Functional Requirements</i>	54
<i>Non-Functional Requirements</i>	105

List of Figures

Fig. 1. TITAN's requirements elicitation process.....	19
Fig. 2. DO's and grape-producing areas in Aragón.....	20
Fig. 3. Wine regions of Veneto.	22
Fig. 4. The export volume of Veneto's wines.....	22
Fig. 5. Illustrative representation of the biosignal data and annotated events (arousals, apneas, hypopneas, desaturations, and sleep stages) recorded in sleep study. EEG = electroencephalogram, EOG = electrooculogram, EMG = electromyography, SpO ₂ = oxygen saturation. N1/N2/N3 = non-rapid eye movement sleep, REM = rapid eye movement sleep.	25
Fig. 6. Typical in-laboratory polysomnography setup used to record biosignals during sleep.	26
Fig. 7. Functional MASTeR Template.	32
Fig. 8. Property MASTeR Template.....	34
Fig. 9. Environment MASTeR Template.	34
Fig. 10. Process MASTeR Template.	35
Fig. 11. Logic MASTeR Template.....	35
Fig. 12. Event MASTeR Template.....	36
Fig. 13. Time MASTeR Template.....	36
Fig. 14. Mapping of assets.....	47
Fig. 15. General infrastructure.....	47
Fig. 16. Architecture flow.	49
Fig. 17. Excerpt from the requirements table.....	50

List of Tables

Table 1. Non-Functional Requirement Categories [23].	33
Table 2. Rules for Individual Requirements [23].	36
Table 3. Forbidden Words [25].	38
Table 4. Quality Goals for the Complete Requirement Set [23].	39
Table 5. Assets summary.	42
Table 6. Requirement Documentation Table Template.	53

List of Abbreviations and Acronyms

Abbreviation	Explanation/ Definition
AI	Artificial Intelligence
CC	Confidential Computing
CocosAI	Confidential Computing System for AI
CVM	Confidential Virtual Machine
DID	Decentralized Identifier
DSSC	Data Spaces Support Centre
EDC	Eclipse Data Space Components
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
EOSC-IF	EOSC Interoperability Framework
EU	European Union
FLT	Federated Learning Toolbox
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
GPU	Graphical Processing Unit
IaC	Infrastructure-as-Code
IdM	Identity Management
IDSA	International Data Spaces Association
IPR	Intellectual Property Rights
MASTeR	Mustergültige Anforderungen - die SOPHIST TEmplates für Requirements
ML	Machine Learning
PDP	Policy Decision Point
PEP	Policy Enforcement Point
PET	Privacy-enhancing technology
PUB	Public
RE	Requirements Engineering
SMPC	Secure Multi-Party Computation
SSI	Self-sovereign Identity
TEE	Trusted Execution Environment

Abbreviation	Explanation/ Definition
TITAN	Trusted environments for confidential computing and secure data sharing
VC	Verifiable Credential
WP	Work package
ZKP	Zero-Knowledge Proof

1 Executive Summary

This document represents deliverable D1.2 of the TITAN project, funded by the European Union, under Grant Agreement No. 101129822 [1]. It presents the initial version of the technical requirements, providing preliminary functional and non-functional requirements for the TITAN software platform solution for confidential data collaboration and secure and privacy-preserving data processing. The technical requirements elicitation and analysis process is outlined reflecting use case and EOSC needs.

This deliverable is integral to all phases of the TITAN project, serving as main reference for all technical design, development, and integration activities. The information presented is preliminary and will evolve throughout the project life cycle, expecting an updated release in month 18. Contributions from activities across other project work packages and tasks are expected to influence the living content of this document.

2 Introduction

The aim of deliverable D1.2 is to explain the initial TITAN requirements, the processes that were conducted, and the results that were achieved within tasks 1.2 and 1.3. Therefore, this document is structured in two main parts. The first part addresses the project and its aim as well as three different data spaces initiatives in secure data sharing. The second part addresses the whole requirements elicitation process, and the requirements list as outcome. The list of requirements described and contained in this deliverable will evolve. That means that during the project, based on discussions, the requirements will be prioritized, filtered, refined. Therefore, this document also contains a reference to a permanent online resource¹, where the latest version of the requirements can always be found.

More in detail, the structure of this document is as follows. Chapter 3 provides an overview of TITAN and its objectives and role in the EOSC ecosystem. Chapter 4 introduces the Data Spaces Support Centre (DSSC), the International Data Spaces Association (IDSA) and Gaia-X in more detail. Chapter 5 provides an overview of the whole requirements elicitation process for secure data sharing and processing, starting with an introduction, followed by the methodology used to collect and to analyse the requirements. The deliverable provides a preview on the final architecture of the TITAN system. Chapter 6 lists all the requirements that were identified until end of third quarter of 2024. Chapter 7 briefly summarizes the requirements numerically. Finally, the permanent online resource and its location is described in Chapter 7.

¹ <https://zenodo.org/records/13990809>

3 Project Summary

3.1. The TITAN Project

The TITAN project proposes to develop secure and trustworthy confidential data processing and sharing capabilities, demonstrated within the EOSC ecosystem. The project emphasises privacy preservation and artificial intelligence (AI) technological solutions in compliance with ethical, regulatory, and legal EU boundaries.

The open-source software platform developed by TITAN will focus on two main use cases: government data and healthcare. Under the umbrella of the EOSC ecosystem, TITAN will leverage an established brand, networks of contacts, working groups, and collaborations with several other concurrent projects.

To promote community adoption of TITAN's open-source software artefacts, the solution will be demonstrated in various vertical cross-border scenarios, notably in public administration and healthcare. TITAN will enhance the EOSC Interoperability Framework (IF) with a platform for confidential data collaboration and secure, privacy-preserving data processing. This platform will enable access to sensitive data sets from public entities and government agencies, ensuring compatibility with the EOSC-IF across technical, semantic, organizational, and legal layers.

3.2. Objectives

TITAN's objectives will be achieved by combining a thorough understanding of the data protection legal landscape on the European Union (EU) and national level with tools from the confidential computing (CC), privacy-enhancing technologies (PETs), machine learning (ML), and distributed ledger technology domains. Emerging hardware-based computation protection technologies such as TEE-supported Confidential Computing used in TITAN's solutions enable novel data access models where both data and applications remain confidential. Leveraging the strengths of distributed ledger technologies to access control, access management and transaction logging will allow to build by design transparency and accountability into TITAN's solutions. Remote attestation features produce cryptographically verifiable statements about computation environments and their security guarantees. TITAN will explore a panoply of privacy-enhancing technologies for data anonymisation and network security best practices to enable solutions to separate security domains within the EOSC.

Objective 1: Collect legal, technical, and architectural requirements and define a platform architecture for secure sharing of sensitive data and publishing anonymised data sets in the EOSC-IF.

Objective 2: Develop secure data sharing and auditing mechanisms for sensitive data, including secure data zones, data access control, and end-to-end data protection (storage - transfer - processing).

Objective 3: Develop an end-to-end secure data processing framework for collaborative and privacy-preserving Machine Learning (ML) using Trusted Execution Environments.

Objective 4: Implement confidential mechanisms, algorithms, and tools with cloud infrastructure platforms and the EOSC-IF and validate solutions in sensitive data-driven use cases (government and healthcare).

Objective 5: Disseminate and promote the solutions for data governance and stewardship through collaboration with EOSC Partnership initiatives, standardisation, and integrating with the EOSC infrastructure.

4 European Data Space Initiatives

This section briefly introduces the concept of data spaces and describes European initiatives and organizations that play a key role in the European data strategy. Finally, the described initiatives' and organizations' importance to the TITAN project is argued.

4.1. Introduction to Data Spaces

Data spaces are becoming increasingly significant in the digital economy due to their ability to facilitate secure and controlled data sharing among different stakeholders. They are especially relevant in sectors like healthcare, manufacturing, finance, and smart cities, where data sharing is critical for innovation, efficiency, and competitiveness. Here's why data spaces are important:

Data Sovereignty and Control

Data spaces provide a framework where data owners retain control over their data, even when shared with other parties. This is crucial for ensuring data sovereignty, where organizations or individuals can dictate how their data is used, shared, or processed. This control is often maintained through standards, policies, and technologies that allow for permissions, restrictions, and secure transactions.

Interoperability

Data spaces enable interoperability across different systems, platforms, and organizations. This interoperability is essential for creating an integrated ecosystem where data from different sources can be combined, analysed, and utilized effectively. By adhering to common standards, data spaces ensure that data can be shared and understood across diverse entities.

Innovation and Collaboration

By providing a secure environment for data exchange, data spaces foster innovation and collaboration. Organizations can share non-sensitive data, or even sensitive data under strict conditions, to drive research, develop new products, or optimize services. For example, in healthcare, data spaces allow different stakeholders to share medical data for research while protecting patient privacy.

Trustworthy Data Sharing

Data spaces are designed to build trust among participants. They use technologies like encryption, blockchain, and access controls to ensure that data is shared securely and that its integrity is maintained. This trust is fundamental to encouraging organizations to participate in data sharing without fear of data breaches or misuse.

Economic Growth

By unlocking data that would otherwise remain siloed within organizations, data spaces contribute to economic growth. They allow businesses to leverage external data to improve decision-making, optimize operations, and create new revenue streams. This is especially

important in data-driven industries where access to diverse datasets can provide a competitive edge.

Regulatory Compliance

In regions with stringent data protection regulations, such as the European Union with the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR), data spaces offer a way to share data while remaining compliant with legal requirements. They ensure that data handling practices align with privacy laws, thereby reducing the risk of legal penalties and enhancing public trust.

Data-Driven Decision Making

Organizations within a data space can access a richer and more diverse set of data, leading to better-informed decisions. Whether for public policy, business strategy, or operational improvements, access to comprehensive data sets can significantly enhance the quality and accuracy of decision-making processes.

Cross-Sector Benefits

Data spaces often enable cross-sector data sharing, leading to new insights and innovations that wouldn't be possible within a single sector. For example, data from the transportation sector could be used in urban planning to reduce traffic congestion, or environmental data could be shared with energy companies to optimize resource use.

Conclusion

Data spaces are vital for the future of digital transformation. They create an ecosystem where data can be shared securely, controlled by its owners, and used in innovative ways that benefit society, businesses, and economies. As digital ecosystems continue to expand, the importance of data spaces will only grow, making them a cornerstone of modern data management strategies.

4.2. Gaia-X

Gaia-X is a European initiative that was launched in 2019. Its goal is to establish a basis for cross-company data sharing while maintaining data sovereignty. The focus is on an architecture that includes both a technical infrastructure and an organizational business layer. A special vision is to create a trustworthy and decentralized data ecosystem based on EU values and de-facto standards through the development of a series of strategies, rules, specifications, and a compliance framework. The **Gaia-X European Association for Data and Cloud AISBL** forms the core of the organizational structure. It is an international non-profit association under Belgian law (French: association internationale sans but lucratif, abbreviated AISBL). It was established to develop the technical framework and operate the services of the Gaia-X Federation.

The association was officially founded in January 2021 by 22 companies and organizations. To date, over 300 members have joined, and more are welcome. Members commit to upholding the values of data protection, transparency, openness, security, and respect for data rights. These members include companies that provide or use data infrastructures, IT start-ups, research institutions, or business associations.

Gaia-X promotes the establishment of decentralized architectures. The goal is to make data available where it is generated or stored. According to standard data sharing agreements,

different roles and responsibilities exist within a decentralized data space: **Provider**, **Consumer**, and **Operator**. Multiple roles can also be realized by a single actor. Providers include data holders and offer data and/or services. Consumers are the data users and therefore obtain these services from Providers. Operators act as intermediaries between these parties, facilitating matchmaking, serving as trust anchors, or conducting audits, among other functions. In addition to technology, governance constitutes a fundamental pillar of the ecosystem. All participants in the system accept the common rules and commit to adhering to them. To learn more about the architecture, you can find additional information in the official Gaia-X Architecture Document².

To achieve a technical implementation according to the Gaia-X principles, connectors are employed to interconnect the various participants in an interoperable manner. An example of this is the Eclipse Dataspace Components (EDC). Within this gateway tool, identities are managed, access and usage conditions are defined, and data is linked.

To demonstrate Gaia-X compliance, labels from one of the six Gaia-X Digital Clearing Houses are used (as of October 2024). A clearing house consists of three mandatory and three additional optional components. The mandatory components include:

- **Gaia-X Registry:** This service establishes the Gaia-X Registry as outlined in the Architecture Document. It serves as the foundation for ecosystem governance by storing the Trust Anchors recognized by the Gaia-X Trust Framework. Additionally, it contains the shapes and schemas necessary for validating compliance with Gaia-X, along with other pertinent details, such as the Terms and Conditions for compliance service users.
- **Gaia-X Compliance:** It verifies Gaia-X Credentials to ensure conformity with the guidelines outlined in the compliance document or Trust Framework, and it signs those that are deemed valid.
- **Gaia-X Notarization Service:** The Gaia-X notarization service for registration numbers operates as the Gaia-X Notary. This tool is utilized to verify the authenticity of all registration numbers provided by participants within their Participant Credentials.

Ultimately, there are four levels of compliance, with the lowest level being sufficient to be considered compliant. To learn more about the architecture, you can find additional information in the official Gaia-X Compliance Document³.

4.3. International Data Spaces Associations (IDSA)

To establish a uniform standard for data exchange within the industry and research domains, the **International Data Spaces Association⁴ (IDSA)** was founded and has devised the International Data Spaces Reference Architecture Model (IDS-RAM) [2]. The IDSA is a non-profit organization and consists of more than 140 member companies [3]. These members include major companies such as Audi, Mercedes-Benz, Fraunhofer, Google, Microsoft, Siemens, Telekom, and many more [4]. The first version of the IDS-RAM was

² <https://docs.gaia-x.eu/technical-committee/architecture-document/latest/>

³ <https://docs.gaia-x.eu/policy-rules-committee/compliance-document/24.06/>

⁴ <https://internationaldataspaces.org>

released in 2017. Currently, the fourth version of the IDS-RAM is developed and publicly available on GitHub [2]. The latest version is version 4.2, which has been released in March 2023. In addition to the development of the IDS-RAM, the association offers a certification program, trainings, and development measures for small and medium-sized enterprises [3], [5].

4.4. Data Spaces Support Centre (DSSC)

The **Data Spaces Support Centre**⁵ (DSSC) aims to help create common data spaces. These spaces will collectively form a sovereign, interoperable, and trustworthy environment for data sharing, allowing data to be reused within and across various sectors. They strive to uphold EU values and support the European economy and society. Funded by the European Commission under the Digital Europe Program, the Centre targets the public sector and companies interested in establishing sovereign data spaces. The Data Spaces Support Centre plans to identify the needs of data space initiatives, set common requirements, and establish best practices. This effort is intended to speed up the development of sovereign data spaces, which are essential for digital transformation across all sectors. Leveraging the combined expertise of its 12 consortium partners, the Centre aims to offer the best possible support to initiatives focused on creating interoperable data spaces.

The DSSC supports the data space community by following a structured heartbeat and release cycle. They create numerous resources in collaboration with the Community of Practice (CoP). The Centre promotes the adoption of data spaces through a variety of support activities, including a platform for knowledge and asset sharing, a help desk, toolboxes, and active interaction with the CoP. These support options are tailored to meet the needs of data space initiatives at various stages of development. The DSSC's work will continuously adapt with a user-centric approach, driven by co-creation with stakeholders and the exchange of lessons and experiences among different data spaces.

An important achievement of the DSSC is the definition of a **blueprint** for building data spaces. The blueprint is a thorough and consistent set of guidelines designed to support the development cycle of data spaces. It encompasses the conceptual model of a data space, essential building blocks, and recommended standards and specifications. The DSSC uses an asset-based approach to provide value to users. Some assets are part of the Data Spaces Blueprint and cover a range from introductory information to detailed knowledge about standards. The following assets are available and are relevant to the overall Data Spaces Blueprint rather than a specific building block: Glossary, Concept Model, and Data Spaces Building Blocks.

4.5. Importance of Data Spaces for TITAN

Data spaces are essential to TITAN's success and functionality, as they facilitate the secure data sharing that TITAN is striving to achieve. The project will employ cutting-edge data space technologies to enable privacy-preserving data sharing. The following outlines the key contributions of data spaces to TITAN and, by extension, to EOSC. The various data spaces

⁵ <https://dssc.eu>

initiatives contribute to the TITAN system by providing sources for functional requirements. Additionally, the data spaces standards introduced by IDSA and DSSC resulted in open source implementations of so-called data space connectors. These connectors will be a software component enabling secure and sovereign data exchange between the data providers and data consumers.

Facilitating Cross-Border Collaboration

Data spaces enable researchers from various domains and geographic locations to share and access data securely. This cross-border collaboration is crucial for addressing global challenges, such as climate change, pandemics, and sustainable development, by pooling resources and knowledge.

Ensuring Data Interoperability

Data spaces within TITAN and EOSC ensure that data from different sources and formats can be seamlessly integrated and used together. This interoperability is essential for combining datasets from various scientific disciplines, which is key to fostering interdisciplinary research. Standardized data formats and protocols within data spaces help researchers to easily exchange and understand data.

Enhancing Data Sovereignty and Trust

Data sovereignty, or the ability of data owners to control their data, is a fundamental principle in TITAN and EOSC. Data spaces allow researchers and institutions to share their data under specific conditions, ensuring that they retain control over how their data is used and who can access it. This builds trust among participants, encouraging more open and extensive data sharing.

Supporting Compliance with Data Regulations

Europe has stringent data protection laws, such as the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) [6]. Data spaces within TITAN and EOSC help ensure that data sharing and usage comply with these regulations. By providing a framework for secure and lawful data exchange, data spaces help researchers to avoid legal issues and protect sensitive information, such as personal or medical data.

Driving Innovation and Scientific Discovery

EOSC aims to unlock the potential of big data in science by providing access to vast amounts of data across disciplines. Data spaces contribute to this by enabling the sharing and re-use of research data, which can lead to new discoveries, more robust scientific methodologies, and the development of new tools and technologies. Researchers can leverage data spaces to access diverse datasets, leading to more comprehensive and innovative research outcomes.

Economic and Social Impact

By making research data more accessible and interoperable through data spaces, EOSC can accelerate scientific advancements that have significant economic and social impacts. For example, faster and more efficient research can lead to quicker development of medical treatments, new technologies, and sustainable solutions to environmental challenges. Data spaces are thus central to maximizing the impact of EOSC on society.

Supporting the FAIR Data Principles

EOSC promotes the FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable) data principles, which are essential for open science. Data spaces are integral to achieving these principles by ensuring that data is organized, stored, and shared in ways that make it easily discoverable, usable, and interoperable by others. This contributes to a more open and effective scientific ecosystem.

Enabling a Scalable and Sustainable Infrastructure

As EOSC grows, it needs a scalable and sustainable infrastructure to manage the increasing amounts of data. Data spaces provide a decentralized but interconnected environment, where data can be managed efficiently across various platforms and institutions. This scalability is crucial for the long-term sustainability of the EOSC.

Conclusion

Data spaces are crucial for EOSC and the TITAN project, providing the infrastructure needed to support secure, interoperable, and compliant data sharing across Europe. They enhance collaboration, drive innovation, and ensure that the vast amounts of data generated by scientific research can be effectively used to tackle some of the world's most pressing challenges.

5 Technical Requirements Elicitation and Analysis

5.1. Introduction

This section provides an introduction into requirements engineering as a discipline in software engineering and its application in TITAN.

The requirements elicitation process is distributed over the tasks T1.1, T1.2, and T1.3:

- **T1.1/D1.1:** Legal, regulatory, and ethical requirements for EOSC secure data sharing and processing
- **T1.2/D1.2:** Technical Requirements for EOSC secure data sharing and processing
- **T1.3/D1.2:** Functional and non-functional requirements for EOSC collaborative AI platform

This deliverable deals with the requirements for the tasks T1.2 and T1.3, while D1.1 contains the legal, regulatory, and ethical parts.

Requirements Engineering (RE) is a process in software engineering [7] that covers the early phases of the software life cycle [8] and aims to capture, describe, and check the requirements of the system to be created [9].

According to recent literature, new requirements for a system are created iteratively and incrementally if the requirements cannot be fully captured at the start of a project [10], [11]. Particularly in projects where not all functionalities of the system can be predicted in advance, RE must be viewed as a cross-phase process and not as an independent phase [11]. In TITAN, this was considered right from the start by planning two subsequent iterations for the requirements elicitation.

In literature RE is defined as “a systematic and disciplined approach to the specification and management of requirements with the following three objectives” [9]:

1. to “know relevant requirements, to establish consensus among the stakeholders involved into the requirements, to design the documentation of the requirements in accordance with specified standards and to manage the requirements systematically”.
2. to “understand and document the customer's wants and needs”.
3. to “specify and manage the requirements in order to reduce the risk of delivering a system that does not meet the customer's wants and needs”.

Interacting requirements are a common source for errors [12], where manual dependency analysis is time consuming and costly [13]. According to Gotel and Finkelstein [14] “Requirements traceability refers to the ability to describe and follow the life of a requirement, in both a forwards and backwards direction (i.e., from its origins, through its development and specification, to its subsequent deployment and use, and through all periods of on-going refinement and iteration in any of these phases).” while the ISO/IEC/IEEE Systems and software engineering – Vocabulary [15] defines requirements traceability as “the identification and documentation of the derivation path (upward) and allocation/flow-down path (downward) of requirements in the requirements hierarchy.” and as “[a] discernible association between a requirement and related requirements, implementations, and verifications.”.

Tracing is the most common and effective way to track requirements through a software project [16] and mandatory in various safety and security critical domains [17]. Possibilities to establish trace links range from simple references of complete documents to individual, identifiable, typed, and possibly attributed connections between elements within development artifacts. Different approaches exist to specify and maintain [18] various types of trace links [19]. We aim at explicit, material, and typed links conforming to a traceability model defining the possible trace links and traceable objects [20]

Requirements Management is a sub-process in the RE process that involves understanding and controlling changes to system requirements [8]. An important task of requirements management is to monitor requirements and maintain the links between requirements so that when changes occur, the impact on requirements that are also affected can be assessed. Requirements management should start by planning the management of changes to requirements alongside requirements elicitation, even if the tasks only begin with the first draft of the overall system specification [8].

The University's of Koblenz (UKO) and Fraunhofer ISST's (FRA) expert knowledge, pre-acquired in various projects, contributed to defining the methods and practices for the elicitation of TITAN's technical requirements. In addition, UKO, and FRA act as the requirements management board for TITAN's entire requirements elicitation phase.

In general, the focus of the elicitation process lies on:

- Defining a coherent scope,
- avoiding requirements communication misunderstandings between stakeholders,
- and maintaining requirements through stages of uncertainty and change.

To achieve these goals, UKO has defined criteria for legal, ethical, and technical requirements elicitation according to system and software engineering standards and best practices. These criteria were discussed and agreed upon in the project consortium.

Thus, UKO provided a requirements list template with accompanying documentation of the criteria that were used during the requirements collection phase.

The same approach was applied in tasks T1.1 and T1.3 and serves as basis for D1.1. To avoid redundancies, the methodology is only described in D1.2.

5.2. Methodology

The requirements elicitation process for TITAN was built upon scientific and practical knowledge in requirements engineering. The process consists of the following three steps that are explained in detail in the respective sections (see Fig. 1):

1. **Preparation.** Definition of common elicitation criteria, templates, and quality goals (see section 0)
2. **Collection.** Capturing non-functional and functional requirements from stakeholder perspective (see section 0)
3. **Elicitation and analysis.** Quality assurance and consolidation of preliminary requirement lists (see section 5.7)

The two use cases (see section 5.3) that are employed to show the applicability and capabilities of the TITAN approach contributed to the technical, ethical, and legal requirements.

Steps 2 and 3 are an interactive process between the partners, the system use case providers, and the asset providers to determine the user and system requirements. Requirements are collected, classified, prioritised, and specified. These steps are repeated until all requirements are collected and the participants are satisfied with the result.

Fig. 1. TITAN's requirements elicitation process.

5.3. Use Cases

To show TITAN's capabilities, two use cases were developed that encompass secure and data sharing and processing. The first use case originates from the public sector, the second from the healthcare domain. The TITAN project aims to deliver integrations and demonstrators that enable execution of these use cases in a secure and confidential way.

5.3.1. Use Case 1: Confidential sharing and collaboration with sensitive agrifood government data

5.3.1.1. Aragón region

Aragón is a renowned grape-producing region with a rich tradition and culture of viticulture, covering approximately 36,470 hectares of vineyards, which include various Denominations of Origin (DO) and a wide range of grape varieties. The main DOs in Aragón - Calatayud, Cariñena, Campo de Borja, and Somontano - account for about 80% of the region's total wine production.

Fig. 2 illustrates the wine-producing areas of Aragón, showing the DO regions (left) and the Protected Geographical Indication (IGP) "Vinos de la Tierra" production zones (right).

Fig. 2. DO's and grape-producing areas in Aragón.

The wine industry plays a crucial role in Aragón's agri-food sector, with the economic benefits remaining largely within the region, as the transformation process occurs near the vineyards. Last year alone, wine exports generated 124.1 million euros, making internationalization a key driver of the sector's success. However, the industry faces significant challenges, particularly in maintaining high standards of quality and meeting international demand. To do so, modern production systems require advanced technologies and efficient controls throughout the production and commercialization stages, ensuring consumers receive wines with the highest quality, origin, and aging guarantees.

One of the major collaborations underway involves the Aragón government and local winegrowers, aiming to address the challenges of sustainability and disease control in viticulture. By introducing predictive models to minimize the use of fungicides and the frequency of their application, this partnership seeks to promote sustainable farming practices while ensuring higher quality and safer products for consumers.

The pilot project in Aragón focuses on *vitis vinifera*, primarily the *garnacha*, *mazuela*, *tempranillo*, and *chardonnay* grape varieties. The key diseases targeted by this project are *Mildew*, *Sparganothis pilleriana*, *Lobesia botrana* (grape moth), *Powdery mildew*, and *Botrytis cinerea*.

To begin the pilot, two representative areas, Cariñena and Campo de Borja, have been selected for experimental vineyards, where meteorological stations and other measurement equipment will be installed. In each area, two adjacent fields will be used: a control field,

which will receive standard fungicide treatments as determined by the growers, and a testing field, which will only be treated when the predictive model developed as part of the project indicates a need. This setup aims to demonstrate that predictive models can significantly contribute to sustainable agriculture, achieving three key objectives:

1. Environmental benefits.
2. Enhanced food safety and consumer protection.
3. Increased profitability by optimizing costs.

Developing this predictive model will require integrating various data sources. First, it will incorporate methods for predicting the most prevalent diseases affecting vineyards. These models will then be enhanced through machine learning and Big Data to improve accuracy, allowing adjustments for regional variables.

Key data sources include:

- Meteorological data from the Agroclimatic Information System for Irrigation (SIAR) network and Spain's State Meteorological Agency (AEMET), which provide critical weather data like temperature, humidity, wind, and precipitation.
- Phenological and disease data from Aragón's Phytosanitary Surveillance Network (FARA), which offers field observation data on the phenological stages and disease status of crops, as well as meteorological data from its own network of stations. It is important to note that the phenological and disease data hold a confidential status due to the sensitive nature of this information. Public disclosure of such data could have significant consequences, including fluctuations in wine prices or unwarranted alarm among farmers.
- Satellite imagery from the Copernicus observation program, which will be analysed to assess the effects of humidity and climate on crops. However, it is important to highlight that while satellite imagery can detect environmental factors affecting the vineyards, such as moisture levels or weather impacts, it lacks the precision necessary to directly identify specific plant diseases.

With these data inputs, the project will develop disease, phenological, and meteorological models to achieve accurate simulation models, which will be further refined through machine learning techniques. The goal is to create a 3-day prediction model for powdery mildew and a 7-day prediction model for mildew and other diseases.

The predictive models will be validated by testing them in vineyard areas not used for model training, including other Aragonese vineyards such as Somontano de Barbastro, Calatayud, and IGP regions like Valle del Cinca and Ribera del Gállego-Cinco Villas. Additionally, data from international vineyards, such as those in Thessalonica, will be considered for broader validation.

5.3.1.2. Veneto region

The Veneto region, located in northeastern Italy, is Italy's leading wine-producing region, both in terms of volume and quality. With a long history of viticulture, its diverse climate and soil types support a wide range of wine styles. Veneto produces approximately 10 to 12 million hectolitres of wine annually, accounting for around 20-25% of Italy's total wine production (45 to 50 million hectolitres per year, see Fig. 3).

Approximately 3 million hectolitres of Veneto's wine are exported annually, representing 30-35% of the total wine exports from Italy, the world's largest wine exporter. Economically,

Veneto's wine exports contribute around €2 billion annually, constituting approximately 25% of Italy's total wine export revenue.

Fig. 3. Wine regions of Veneto.

The region produces a balanced mix of white (approximately 55%) and red wines (approximately 45%) across 28 DOC (Denomination of Controlled Origin) and 14 DOCG (Denomination of Controlled and Guaranteed Origin) regions. Notable production areas include Prosecco DOCG, Amarone della Valpolicella DOCG, and Soave DOC (see Figure 4).

With 70% of its production exported, Prosecco is one of the world's most popular sparkling wines. The United States, Germany, the United Kingdom, and China are the primary markets for Veneto's wines. Fig. 4 provides a breakdown of exports by production area.

Fig. 4. The export volume of Veneto's wines.

Wineries' diseases and use of pesticides in Veneto Region

As in other wine-producing regions, vineyards in Veneto face various diseases and pests that can significantly impact grape quality, yield, and wine quality. To combat these issues, growers commonly employ pesticides and integrated pest management strategies.

Given the region's humid, rainy, and windy climate, several fungal diseases can affect grapevines. Among the most concerning are *Powdery Mildew (Oidium)*, *Downy Mildew*

(*Peronospora*), *Botrytis Bunch Rot (Gray Mold)*, and *Esca Disease* (a wood disease leading to vine death).

Additionally, a bacterial disease known as *Grapevine Flavescence Dorée (FD)* is caused by *phytoplasma* and transmitted by the leafhopper insect *Scaphoideus titanus*. Like *Botrytis*, which is spread by the *Lobesia Botrana* moth, FD is another insect-borne pest.

To combat various diseases and pests, Veneto's vineyards employ a combination of strategies: **Chemical Treatments:** Fungicides, insecticides, and herbicides are applied throughout the growing season to target specific pests and diseases; **Organic Practices:** Organic methods, such as using natural predators and botanical pesticides, are employed to minimize chemical input; **Integrated Pest Management (IPM):** IPM combines various techniques, including monitoring, cultural practices, and targeted treatments, to minimize pest and disease impacts; **Cultural Practices:** Proper canopy management, pruning, and improving air circulation within the vineyard can help reduce disease pressure and the need for chemical treatments.

Despite these efforts, the use of pesticides remains high, leading to several challenges: **Pesticide Resistance:** Overreliance on chemical treatments can lead to the development of resistant pests and diseases; **Environmental Impact:** Pesticide use can harm beneficial insects, soil health, and water quality; **Regulatory Changes:** The European Union's stricter regulations on pesticide use are driving the need for more sustainable practices.

In the Veneto region, data concerning grape diseases and pesticide use are produced, collected, and analysed through a coordinated effort involving several entities. These include government bodies, research institutions, agricultural organizations, and individual growers. The aim is to monitor vineyard health, optimize pest management strategies, and comply with regulatory standards. Considered data sources are:

- a) Vineyard care in Veneto involves an elaborated system of monitoring and surveillance. Agronomists, viticultural technicians (such as those from the Consorzio di Tutela della Valpolicella or the Consorzio di Tutela del Prosecco DOC), and growers regularly inspect their plots to detect diseases, pests, and signs of stress in the vines. Additionally, the phenology of the plants is closely monitored to adjust cultural practices at the optimal time. Technology also plays a fundamental role. The use of drones and satellite imagery allows for the early detection of disease outbreaks, monitoring vine vigor and canopy health. The Veneto's Phytosanitary Services play a crucial role in regional surveillance. They collect data on vine health, the incidence of diseases and pests, and the phenological evolution of vineyards. Samples are taken and laboratory analyses are carried out when necessary. To investigate new disease control strategies, experimental vineyards are maintained. In collaboration with research institutions and universities, such as the University of Padua, trials are conducted with pesticides and biological control measures. This multifaceted approach ensures early detection of problems, allowing for a rapid and effective response to protect vines and ensure the production of high-quality wines.
- b) The Veneto has a network of weather stations providing meteorological data such as temperature, humidity, rainfall, and wind patterns which are crucial for predicting disease outbreaks, particularly the spread of fungal diseases (e.g., downy mildew).
- c) Agro-meteorological models use this data to forecast disease risks, such as downy and powdery mildew, allowing for more targeted pesticide applications.

- d) Farming practices: field notebooks which are required by the European Common Agrarian Policy (CAP) regulation gather information about the farming practices (e.g. the use of pesticides). Field practices and field notebook are supported by Farm Management Software and Digital Platforms which also support making informed decisions.

The data collected from various sources is utilized to develop disease risk models and forecasts. Agro-meteorological models and predictive algorithms analyse weather data, including temperature, leaf wetness, and relative humidity, to assess the risk of disease outbreaks such as downy and powdery mildew. The analysis results inform Integrated Pest Management (IPM) planning, aiming to minimize chemical inputs while effectively controlling diseases. It is anticipated that the models developed through TITAN, driven by artificial intelligence, will surpass the performance of current data-driven models.

5.3.1.3. Common definition of the Use Case 1

The objective of the confidential sharing and collaboration with sensitive agrifood government data use case will be to use data gathered both in the Aragón and Veneto regions to create phenology and pest risk machine learning models which outperforms the results of the current used models. This will mean to integrate data of sources which would be available in both regions:

- Meteorological data: from meteorological stations, weather forecast, etc.
- Meteorological data derived indexes: indexes derived for modelling phenology and pest risk using “classical” approaches (not AI driven). If not available, it would be interesting to be calculated to feed AI models with agronomist knowledge.
- Vegetal indexes derived from Copernicus Sentinel 2 multispectral images: they can be obtained from Copernicus Data Space for free with some quota restrictions but requires having the polygon which define the geographical location of the vineyards (e.g., in Spain it can be obtained from the Spanish Cadastral Registry).
- Field observations of the phenological stages of the vineyards and of the presence of pests. An analysis of the quality of the available pest data will determine which models will be created. However, it seems that *oidio*, *lobesia botrana* (as a transmission factor of *botrytis*) and *botrytis* could be the more significant models because of their presence in both regions.

Regarding the confidentiality of the data the data, because of their link with cultural farming practices, field observations use will require the higher level of protection.

5.3.2. Use Case 2: Collaborative Use of ML in Healthcare

In medical research, machine learning has been utilized to analyze sensitive medical data in various applications. To obtain accurate results, these machine-learning solutions often require a huge amount of data which often is sensitive in nature in the field of medical research. However, using, sharing, and combining sensitive data from multiple clinical or research institutions can be extremely difficult or even impossible. As a result, the developed models might need to rely on data from a single source or homogenous population; this raises the question of whether the models can be generalized to other patient populations or data from other sources. In addition, maintaining the privacy of the sensitive data is the highest priority; however, this can hinder the openness of scientific research, and thus, following FAIR principles, GDPR, and national laws and regulations.

Fig. 5. Illustrative representation of the biosignal data and annotated events (arousals, apneas, hypopneas, desaturations, and sleep stages) recorded in sleep study. EEG = electroencephalogram, EOG = electrooculogram, EMG = electromyography, SpO₂ = oxygen saturation. N1/N2/N3 = non-rapid eye movement sleep, REM = rapid eye movement sleep.

In this medical use case, UEF, CHA, and INS will test the usability and performance of the Confidential EOSC platform. From the aspects of the medical field, this use case will especially focus on the field of sleep medicine. The goal is to develop deep learning-based solutions for the diagnostics and severity estimation of sleep disorders, such as sleep apnea as well as their health consequences. These models will be developed by utilizing biosignal data (e.g. electroencephalography (EEG), electrocardiogram (ECG), breathing patterns, and blood oxygen saturation, Fig. 5) recorded during sleep studies (Fig. 6) as well as patients' medical records and questionnaires describing, for example, patients' quality of life and subjective sleep quality. CHA and INS will provide real-world healthcare data from their sleep clinics and UEF will provide research-orientated sleep data collected at their SmartSleep Lab (<https://sites.uef.fi/star/smartsleeplab/>). This data will be utilized in the deep learning approaches developed by UEF and implemented into the platform. In addition, this use case will test the developed secure data sharing, federated learning from ZEN, and trusted execution environments from CAB and UVC.

Fig. 6. Typical in-laboratory polysomnography setup used to record biosignals during sleep.

5.4. EOSC Interoperability Framework

The EOSC Interoperability Framework (EOSC-IF) is designed to ensure seamless integration and collaboration between different research communities, data providers, and infrastructures across Europe. This requires a set of technical requirements to guarantee that the data, services, and tools within the EOSC ecosystem can be accessed, shared, and used in a standardized and interoperable manner. The key technical requirements of the EOSC-IF can be broken down into the following categories (cf. [21]):

- Technical Interoperability
- Semantic Interoperability
- Organizational Interoperability
- Syntactic Interoperability
- Legal Interoperability
- Service Interoperability
- Security and Trust
- Infrastructure Interoperability
- Support for Persistent Identifiers

The individual categories are explained in the following sections,

Technical Interoperability

This refers to the ability of systems and services to exchange data and to make use of the exchanged information in a meaningful way. The technical requirements in this category include:

- **Open Standards and Protocols:** EOSC services and data repositories must adhere to widely accepted open standards and communication protocols (e.g., REST, OAI-PMH). These standards facilitate data exchange and integration.
- **APIs and Middleware:** EOSC services should provide standardized APIs (Application Programming Interfaces) and middleware solutions to enable communication between different services, tools, and platforms.
- **Federation of Identity and Access Management (IAM):** EOSC supports federated identity management solutions (e.g., eduGAIN, OpenID Connect) to provide seamless, secure, and trustworthy access to services across different organizations.

Semantic Interoperability

Semantic interoperability ensures that the meaning of data is preserved when shared between different systems, allowing for consistent interpretation. The requirements include:

- **Common Vocabularies and Ontologies:** To ensure that data is understood across different domains, EOSC encourages the use of common vocabularies, taxonomies, and ontologies (e.g., Dublin Core, CERIF).
- **Metadata Standards:** Standardized metadata schemas (e.g., DataCite, DCAT) should be used to describe data in ways that facilitate discovery, integration, and reuse by other researchers.
- **FAIR Data Principles:** Data in EOSC must be Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable, with rich metadata and clear licensing terms to support reuse.

Organizational Interoperability

This category focuses on ensuring that institutions, research groups, and organizations can effectively collaborate and coordinate their resources within EOSC. Key requirements include:

- **Governance and Policies:** A unified governance structure and shared policies across different institutions and service providers to ensure that organizational processes align with EOSC's goals.
- **Service Level Agreements (SLAs):** Clear agreements on the quality, availability, and support of services provided within the EOSC framework.
- **Compliance with Legal and Ethical Standards:** EOSC participants must comply with relevant regulations (e.g., GDPR) and ethical standards regarding data privacy, security, and ownership.

Syntactic Interoperability

Syntactic interoperability is concerned with the format and structure of the data being exchanged. The technical requirements include:

- **Data Formats:** EOSC encourages the use of standardized and widely accepted data formats (e.g., CSV, JSON, XML) to ensure that data can be shared and understood by various systems and tools.
- **Data Serialization Standards:** For data processing and exchange, the EOSC may require serialization standards (e.g., RDF, Turtle, JSON-LD) to ensure consistency in how data is represented.

Legal Interoperability

This addresses the legal aspects of sharing and reusing data across borders and institutions. The requirements include:

- **Standardized Licensing:** Data and services within EOSC must be accompanied by clear, standardized licenses (e.g., Creative Commons, Open Data Commons) to clarify usage rights.
- **Data Protection and Privacy Compliance:** All participants must comply with GDPR and other relevant data protection laws, ensuring that personal and sensitive data is handled appropriately.

Service Interoperability

Service interoperability ensures that various services (e.g., data repositories, computing resources, analysis tools) can work together within EOSC. Key requirements include:

- **Service Discovery:** Services within EOSC must be easily discoverable and indexed using common catalogues and registries.
- **Orchestration and Workflow Integration:** EOSC needs to support the integration of different services into workflows. Workflow tools and service orchestration protocols (e.g., CWL, WDL) are needed for seamless integration.
- **Modular and Composable Services:** Services within EOSC should be modular and composable, meaning that they can be combined in different ways to create complex workflows or research environments.

Security and Trust

Ensuring the security and trustworthiness of data and services within EOSC is a priority. The technical requirements include:

- **Data Encryption:** Secure data transfer protocols (e.g., TLS, SSL) and encryption standards to protect data during exchange.
- **Authentication and Authorization:** Strong mechanisms for user authentication and authorization, possibly based on federated identity solutions.
- **Audit and Monitoring:** Continuous monitoring of services and data access for auditing and ensuring compliance with security standards.

Infrastructure Interoperability

The infrastructure layer focuses on ensuring that the physical and virtual resources that support EOSC are interoperable. Requirements include:

- **Federated Cloud and HPC Resources:** Integration of computing resources such as cloud services and High-Performance Computing (HPC) across multiple providers, following standardized protocols.
- **Containerization and Virtualization:** The use of containers (e.g., Docker, Kubernetes) and virtualization technologies to ensure reproducibility and scalability of scientific applications across different infrastructures.
- **Scalability and Elasticity:** The ability of the EOSC infrastructure to scale as the data and computing needs of the research community grow.

Support for Persistent Identifiers (PIDs)

EOSC requires the use of persistent identifiers (e.g., DOIs, ORCID, ARK) for datasets, researchers, and institutions to ensure that resources can be reliably referenced over time.

Conclusion

The EOSC interoperability framework emphasizes open standards, FAIR data principles, and the seamless integration of services, ensuring that data and tools from different domains, regions, and systems can be accessed, shared, and reused in a secure, compliant, and efficient manner.

5.5. Preparation

The first phase of the requirements elicitation process in TITAN is the preparation phase. In this phase, UKO, as requirements engineering expert, defined criteria and provided a template for requirements elicitation as well as a cheat sheet with all the rules for understanding the criteria and formulating the requirements. Both were presented to the partners involved in WP1 and complemented by ideas from partners. In addition, further ambiguities were clarified in partner discussions during the regular bi-weekly WP1 meetings. Thus, a common understanding was achieved.

5.5.1. Elicitation Criteria

For TITAN's requirements elicitation the following criteria and attributes were defined and provided as a legend to the partner. A definition table is provided in Table 6.

Requirement ID

The unique requirement ID for reference and traceability purposes.

Type

The type of the requirement is one of *legal*, *ethical*, *functional*, *property/environment*, *non-functional*, *process*, or *document*. Legal requirements are referring to regulations and law. Technical requirements are encompassing functional and non-functional requirements. Thereby, functional requirements may define system functionality, interactions between components, interactions to achieve user goals, and others. Further, they may refer to implementation technologies or data formats, APIs or pre-existing services that can be utilized in TITAN.

In addition, non-functional requirements can also be so-called meta requirements of type *document*. Meta requirements address the form and structure of the individual requirements and the documentation. Meta requirements are fulfilled by the requirements documents themselves, in contrast to ordinary requirements that are to be fulfilled by the system's realisation.

Category

The focus of a requirement is defined by its category. According to ISO/IEC 25010 [22], the main categories used in the requirements elicitation process are functional suitability, performance, efficiency, compatibility, interaction capability, reliability, security, maintainability, flexibility, and safety. For TITAN's requirements, the partners identified the following categories:

- Authentication & Authorization
- Automation
- Data Agreement
- Data Discovery
- Data Sharing
- Documentation
- Documentation Content / IPR
- Documentation Content / Security
- Efficiency

- Feature
- Federated Learning
- General Requirements
- Interoperability
- Metadata
- Monitoring & Traceability
- Network
- Non-linear Operations
- Performance & Sustainability
- Requirement Content
- Scalability
- Security
- Security & Maintainability
- Security & Privacy
- Security/Logging
- Technical
- Usability
- User Interface

Liability

The liability is one of *SHALL*, *SHOULD* or *WILL*. The liabilities are explained in section 5.5.2.

Priority

The priority of the requirement can be either *high*, *medium*, or *low*. In addition to the liability, the priority gives hints to the realisation order. High priority requirements are requirements that must be implemented at first, medium priority requirements are recommended to be developed after the high priority ones, and low priority requirements are requirements which provide a certain additive value to the system, but their fulfilment is not crucial in the beginning.

Subject Matter

The subject matter is the name of the system, subsystem, or actor, that is the subject of the requirements sentence.

Requirement Sentence

A single concrete sentence in the form of one of the MASTeR templates explained in section 5.5.2.

Justification

The justification documents the reason why the requirement is relevant for the project. This can be, e.g., due to legal obligations, GDPR, EOSC-IF or others.

Refers To

References to other documents and applicable standards, as specific as possible.

Author

The name of the author (partner acronym) of the requirement.

Responsible Task

The task numbers of the responsible TITAN tasks that contribute to the realisation and fulfilment of the requirement.

Source (Stakeholder)

Sources are names of stakeholders for which the requirements are relevant.

Comments

Additional comments contain any additional information that is valuable to understand the requirement.

5.5.2. Requirement Templates

In general, requirements quality improves when clear rules for the formulation of the requirements are defined and followed. To support this, template systems to structure the requirement descriptions are used. In TITAN, requirements follow the so-called Sophist MASTeR templates that have emerged from knowledge and experience in a wide range of projects [23]. MASTeR is a German acronym for “Mustergültige Anforderungen - die SOPHIST TEmplates für Requirements”, in English “Immaculate requirements - the SOPHIST TEmplates for Requirements”. The short summary of the template system in this section explains its purpose and application.

There is a basic template for functional requirements as well as three templates for non-functional requirements. The latter are meant for property, environment, and process requirements. These templates can be extended by an optional part for logical, event, and time related conditions. When the template system does not fit all project needs, it can be extended. So far, in TITAN no extension was necessary.

In addition to the templates, a set of rules gives hints for creating understandable and unambiguous requirements of high quality. The templates and rules are explained in the following.

Functional MASTeR

Fig. 7. Functional MASTeR Template.

The MASTeR template system follows simple syntactical rules for the requirements sentences. For example, in the Functional MASTeR template in Fig. 7, the parts in capital letters are keywords that appear literally in the sentence. Parts in square brackets [...] are optional, and parts in angular brackets <...> must be replaced.

Each sentence must contain one of the liability keywords SHALL (mandatory), SHOULD (optional), or WILL (mandatory, but realized in future).

Functional requirements come in three flavours. We will give examples from TITAN for each.

1. **Independent System Activities** (path “-“)

Describes activities of the system that are executed autonomously without user interaction.

Example: *The system SHALL apply an authentication and authorisation solution that could be federated.*

2. **User Interaction** (path “PROVIDE...”)

Describes functionality that require user interaction. The system enables users to perform a function to achieve a goal.

Example: *The authentication system SHALL PROVIDE the users THE ABILITY TO choose the specific data that will be shared during an authentication and authorization process.*

3. **Interface Requirements** (path “BE ABLE TO”)

Describes requirements that deal with integration of external systems.

Example: *The system SHALL BE ABLE TO maintain access to the blockchain network.*

Non-Functional Requirements

The remaining three basic templates are used to formulate non-functional requirements. They describe system properties, the system’s operating environment, and requirements for the development and maintenance process. The following table shows different types of non-functional requirements and the applicable template.

Table 1. Non-Functional Requirement Categories [23].

	Content	Property MASTeR	Environment MASTeR	Process MASTeR
Quality Requirements	Qualitative property of the system of interest (performance requirement)	X		
Technological Requirements	Efficient way to give more accuracy to the scope of a system functionality	X	Environmental Requirements Quantity Requirements	
User Interface Requirements	Details of the visual and acoustic presentation of the user functionality	X		
Requirements for other components	Installation and deployment requirements, tools for assembling components	X		

	Content	Property MASTeR	Environment MASTeR	Process MASTeR
Requirements for Activities to be carried out	Requirements for the development and operation process of the system	X		X
Legal and Contractual Requirements	Agreed rights and legal frameworks that apply to the development and usage of the system	X		X

Property MASTeR

Fig. 8. Property MASTeR Template.

Property requirements denote quality and performance criteria that the system must fulfil.

Example: *The response time of the user interface SHOULD BE less than 5 seconds.*

Environment MASTeR

Fig. 9. Environment MASTeR Template.

Environmental requirements describe conditions that the system and its execution environment must meet.

Example: *The system SHALL BE DESIGNED IN A WAY that the Trusted Execution Environment CAN BE OPERATED on virtual machines with at least 4GB of main memory.*

Process MASTeR

Fig. 10. Process MASTeR Template.

Process requirements define obligations of the development, deployment, and maintenance of the system.

Example: *The data providers SHALL define usage policies that comply to the data protection regulations of the originating country.*

Conditional MASTeR templates

The optional condition parts may be added to address logical, event, and time restrictions. The respective templates are shown here to complete the template definitions. Currently, these conditions are not used in TITAN requirements. The three types of conditional templates are shown in Fig. 11 to Fig. 13.

Fig. 11. Logic MASTeR Template.

Fig. 12. Event MASTeR Template.

Fig. 13. Time MASTeR Template.

5.5.3. Rules for TITAN requirements elicitation

The requirements elicitation in TITAN was conducted by an initial agreement on common rules and criteria. The rules are divided into two groups: rules for individual requirements, and rules for the complete requirement set. These rules are shown in the rest of this section. Many of the rules represent best-practice requirements engineering knowledge, others are quality criteria from international RE standards like ISO/IEC/IEEE 29148:2018 [24].

Rules and quality goals for individual requirements

Each requirement must be complete with respect to the criteria and attributes that were described in section 5.5.1.

Table 2 shows additional rules for individual requirements that were taken from the “SOPHIST REgelwerk for Requirements Engineering” [23]. They were applied in TITAN to achieve high-quality requirements. Table 3 lists forbidden words that are known to introduce ambiguities or misunderstandings, and that may lead to requirements that cannot be tested and validated.

Table 2. Rules for Individual Requirements [23].

Rule #	Priority	Rule	Description
1	Medium	Write every requirement in active voice	Passive voice can delete agents (persons or systems). Add missing agents.
2	Medium	Express every process using unambiguous main verbs.	Imprecise main verbs mask the desired functionality. Chose a verb that expresses the functionality precisely.
3	High	Resolve nominalisations that are not exactly defined and write one or several new requirements with a “good” main verb for every nominalisation.	A nominalisation can mask a whole process. Is this process not sufficiently specified, create new additional requirements with suitable main verbs.

Rule #	Priority	Rule	Description
4	Low	Dissolve light-verb constructions and define the required process, which represents the system's behaviour using a "good" main verb.	A light-verb construction can mask a whole process. Chose a verb that expresses the desired functionality precisely.
5	Medium	Write exactly one requirement statement for each main verb.	Create new requirements for every additional main verb.
6	High	Identify missing Information around the main verb.	Ask the typical 5Ws + 1H (who, what, when, where, why, how) and add missing information.
7	Medium	Identify missing Information around the properties (adjectives/adverbs).	Ask the typical 5Ws + 1H (who, what, when, where, why, how) and add missing information. If the corresponding process is not described sufficiently create a new requirement with a suitable main verb.
8	Medium	Word properties measurable and testable.	Comparative degrees and superlatives always need a reference point.
9	Low	Formulate separate requirements for non-functional aspects if these aspects are independent or needed as a constraint for several functionalities.	Separate the non-functional aspect, if it should be handled independently OR if it is desired comprehensively for several requirements
10	Medium	Analyse numbers and quantities.	Required functions or properties must be applicable to all items of the given portion and no others. If this is not the case, the portion has either to be expanded or restricted. Exceptions must be specified additionally.
11	Medium	Identify missing numbers and quantities.	For every required function or property, the group of items must be defined for which it is applicable.
12	High	Analyse ambiguous nouns.	Ambiguous nouns describe a group of items or actors that is not distinct. Specify them more precisely.
13	Low	Replace formulations that describe possible or impossible situations	Requirements on the possibility or impossibility of functions delete the business logic behind. Identify and add the missing business logic.
14	Low	Remove subordinate clauses that contain irrelevant information for	Motivations and other additional information should be added as

Rule #	Priority	Rule	Description
		the requirement meaning.	comment, not as part of the requirement sentence.
15	Low	Shorten or eliminate flowery expressions or phrases that are irrelevant for your requirement.	Shorten or eliminate flowery expressions or phrases that are irrelevant for your requirement.
16	Medium	Analyse exceptions to the usual behaviour of the system and extend the requirement respective write an additional requirement.	Not only the normal behaviour has to be described, but also the behaviour in exception state.
17	High	Requirements with incomplete conditional structures should be checked and formulated or described by another requirement.	Describe the systems behaviour also for the state that the condition is not fulfilled.
18	High	Write one or more requirements for every implicit assumption not described.	Descriptions can contain implicit assumptions that are preconditions to the description. Key words that indicate implicit assumptions are, for example, temporal or logic processes, or nouns with related describing words. Is an implicit assumption present, that is not described at another point, it must be defined.

Table 3. Forbidden Words [25].

"and/or", "and", "or"	"minimize"	"satisfactory"
"etc."	"maximize"	"adequate"
"goal"	"typical"	"quick"
"shall be included but not limited to"	"rapid"	"first rate"
"relevant"	"user-friendly"	"best possible"
"necessary"	"easy"	"great"
"appropriate"	"sufficient"	"small"
"as far as possible"	"enough"	"large"
"optimize"	"suitable"	"state of the art"

Quality goals for the complete requirement set

In addition to the rules for individual requirements, there are quality criteria for the whole requirements list. These cannot be checked on a single requirement, but only when considering the complete requirement set. Table 4 shows these goals. Requirements that give rise to improvements with respect to the goals were identified and marked to be fixed in the second iteration of TITAN's RE process.

Table 4. Quality Goals for the Complete Requirement Set [23].

Quality Goal	Description
Unique IDs	Each requirement in the TITAN requirements list (D1.1 and D1.2) shall have a unique requirement ID that can be used for reference in other documents, in related requirements, and in realisation artefacts to establish traceability links (e.g., source code, configuration files, deployment descriptors, etc.). Traceability ensures that every realisation artefact can be found easily when a change to the requirement occurs.
No Redundancy	Each requirement shall describe exactly one aspect of the system, and each aspect shall be described in exactly one requirement. This avoids duplicates and largely overlapping requirements that can lead to misunderstandings.
No Conflicts	Conflicting requirements may exist in the requirements list. They shall be clearly identified and refer to each other. At the latest, when a realisation decision is taken, one of the conflicting requirements must be selected and the others marked as not (longer) relevant.
Completeness	Completeness means that the requirements shall mention all possible cases and alternatives, even if some of them will not be realized. This can also be in a form that inapplicable alternatives are at least mentioned and documented. This minimises the likelihood of important facts being overlooked. This goal may be hard to achieve in the first iteration of the RE process. Nevertheless, incompleteness can be identified and fixed for the final requirements list.

5.6. Legal and Technical Requirements Collection

The second phase of the requirements elicitation process is the collection phase. In this phase, various partners involved in WP1 provided requirements according to their expertise. Different data sources were used. Furthermore, the phase was divided into collecting legal requirements and non-technical and technical requirements.

Within bi-weekly meetings, UKO supported the partners and provided relevant feedback to their contributions.

Our structured approach ensured the efficient collection of both legal and technical requirements. To achieve this, we utilized a variety of data sources, and regular meetings promoted collaboration and provided essential feedback among partners and stakeholders. The steps we followed are as follows:

- **Desk Research:** We start by conducting comprehensive literature reviews, which include papers, academic articles, industry reports, and similar publicly available documents from libraries, websites... This step helps us identify relevant standards, frameworks, and solutions applicable to the project.
- **Stakeholder meetings:** We directly engage with key stakeholders from the project pilot use cases. These interviews offer valuable insights into practical challenges and user expectations that desk research alone may not reveal.
- **Best Practices:** We draw upon best practices from previous projects, recognized industry standards (such as ISO, GDPR), and technical guidelines from organizations like the EOSC Interoperability Framework (EOSC IF). This ensures that the requirements are both realistic and fully compliant with current regulations and standards.

The sources we have utilized for requirements collection are as follows:

- Standards and guidelines
 - EOSC IF [21].
 - GDPR [6].
- Feedback from stakeholder interviews
- Prior project experience and lessons learned (TANGO) [26].

5.7. Legal and Technical Requirements Elicitation and Analysis

The third and final phase of the requirements elicitation process was elicitation and analysis. In this phase, the quality of all collected requirements was ensured. It is to be noted that the results in this deliverable only represent the first iteration of TITAN's RE process. The final requirements list will be delivered at M18.

The purpose of the elicitation and analysis is quality assurance of the requirements set with respect to the rules formulated in Section 5.5.3. After the initial requirements collection, the resulting raw list was frozen. As Task Lead, UKO has checked the rules. In case of inconsistencies or rule violations, the identified requirements were pushed back to the author(s) for revision. Then, the resulting requirements list was compiled and again frozen. The list was uploaded to <https://zenodo.org/records/13990809>. All requirements are printed in this deliverable for documentation purposes. Nevertheless, the original source is the uploaded spreadsheet. As a reader of this document, please keep in mind that it only

represents a snapshot of a “living” list that will receive updates during the second iteration of the RE process.

At the time of writing this deliverable, we collected...

- 107 Legal requirements,
- 102 Functional requirements, and
- 35 Non-Functional requirements.

This sums up to 244 requirements in total. As described, the number of requirements is not final and will vary (increase or decrease) during the rest of the project.

The resulting *technical requirements* (functional and non-functional) are part of this deliverable D1.2.

While the requirements elicitation was a joint process, the *legal and ethical requirements* are documented in the project deliverable D1.1 as required by TITANs grant agreement. However, the persistent artefact on Zenodo (cf. Section) contains both parts.

5.8. Preliminary TITAN Software Architecture

This section presents the TITAN architecture, providing an overview along with a comprehensive examination of each asset. We will begin by introducing a table summarizing the assets that compose the architecture, followed by figures that offer a general view of the overall architecture.

5.8.1. Assets summary

The following Table 5 provides an overview of the key assets that constitute the TITAN architecture. For each asset, its name, type, a brief description, the responsible partner, and the corresponding Technology Readiness Level (TRL) are included. The descriptions emphasize how each asset contributes to TITAN's objective of fostering a secure, decentralized, and privacy-focused environment, enabling efficient data management and processing.

Table 5. Assets summary.

	PARTNER	TYPE	DESCRIPTION	Existing TRL
Privacy preserving Identity Management (IdM) with W3C Verifiable Credentials	UMU	License	<p>Privacy preserving Identity Management (IdM) with W3C Verifiable Credentials enables users to securely manage and store their identity information while maintaining control over their privacy (self-sovereign identities). SSI will be the IdM solution used in the data connector of the data sharing platform.</p> <p>Utilizing Decentralized Identifiers (DIDs) and Verifiable Credentials (VCs), individuals can authenticate and prove attributes without revealing unnecessary data. Additionally, cryptographic solutions like Zero-Knowledge Proof (ZKP) are addressed for selective disclosure.</p> <p>Furthermore, sticky policies will be integrated with w3c VC to ensure that data usage rules persist with the data as it is shared across different entities. These policies are embedded within the credential, specifying how the data can be used, stored, and shared. When a verifier requests the credential, they must adhere to these policies, ensuring user consent and control are maintained. This approach enhances privacy and compliance with data protection regulations by enforcing consistent data handling practices. Users benefit from transparency and trust, knowing their data usage preferences are respected throughout its lifecycle.</p>	3

	PARTNER	TYPE	DESCRIPTION	Existing TRL
PEP/PDP	UMU	License	This tool is composed by a Policy Enforcement Point (PEP) and a Policy Decision Point (PDP). The PEP oversees communicating with the user that makes a query for an accessing to a resource and make an action. The PDP is the one which makes the real decision, the user asks for the access and the PDP applies some policies and criterion to know if the user is suitable to make the requested action in the resource.	3
Federated Learning Toolbox	ZEN	Privacy-preserving collaborative AI/ML solution (TITAN ambition Domain 1: confidential collaborative data processing)	Federated Learning Toolbox (FLT) implements the secure orchestration of decentralized Machine Learning workloads processing in TITAN. It enables collaborative AI, general data analysis, and decoupling of private data from the model training without central posting of the data sets, using a secure node and cloud infrastructure. Nodes receive workloads from the server and execute them by downloading the requested container images. The container accesses the local data through the node and executes algorithms with the given parameters.	4
Software support for Confidential GPUs	CAB		GPUs can complete simple and repetitive tasks much faster because it can break the task down into smaller components and finish them in parallel. To preserve the confidentiality and integrity of such tasks and processing, confidential GPUs are required. GPU confidential compute solution relies on a	2

	PARTNER	TYPE	DESCRIPTION	Existing TRL
CocosAI (Confidential Computing System for AI)	UVC	License	<p>confidential virtual machine (CVM) trusted execution environment (TEE) on the CPU, enabled by SEV-SNP on AMD CPUs or by TDX 1.x on Intel CPUs.</p> <p>CocosAI (Confidential Computing System for AI) is a SW system for enabling confidential and privacy-preserving AI/ML, i.e., execution of model training and algorithm inference on confidential data sets. Privacy-preservation is considered a “holy grail” of AI. It opens many possibilities, among which is a collaborative, trustworthy AI. CocosAI leverages Confidential Computing, a novel paradigm based on specialized HW CPU extensions for producing secure encrypted enclaves in memory (Trusted Execution Environments, or TEEs), thus isolating confidential data and programs from the rest of the SW running on the host The final product enables data scientists to train AI and ML models on confidential data that is never revealed, and can be used for Secure Multi-Party Computation (SMPC). AI/ML on combined data sets that come from various sources will unlock huge value.</p>	4
Confidential workload lifecycle manager (Tower)	CAB		Tower is an orchestration service to automate the deployment of Trusted Execution Environments (TEEs) infrastructure resources. It strictly follows Infrastructure-as-Code (IaC) and cloud	4

	PARTNER	TYPE	DESCRIPTION	Existing TRL
Secure Decentralized Data Sharing (ZEN, UVC)			security best practices, putting end users firmly in control of their setups. It offers a set of open-source Terraform configurations to help you manage and provision highly secure run time environments on a wide set of public cloud providers, on-premises, or bare-metal setups.	
	ZEN, UVC	Privacy-preserving collaborative AI/ML solution (TITAN ambition Domain 1: confidential collaborative data processing)	A block-chain-based secure data exchange infrastructure platform with zero-knowledge proofs, encryption-supported Smart Contracts and Decentralized IDs (DIDs) coupled with Verifiable Credentials (VCs).	2
Sleep healthcare data analysis solution based on multi-party ML	CHA, INS, UEF		Computer codes for calculation of new diagnostic parameters (obstruction severity, obstruction duration, desaturation severity, desaturation duration, and adjusted AHI) considering the number, duration, and morphology of individual breathing cessation events.	4
			Computer codes of neural network-based estimation of the apnea-hypopnea index, multiple sleep latency test outcome, sleep structure (sleep stages) from PSG and HSAT signals.	
			Computer codes for automatic exportation and pseudonymization of polysomnographic data from	

	PARTNER	TYPE	DESCRIPTION	Existing TRL
Machine learning (ML) models for agriculture disease predictions and support-decisions system			<p>various commercial PSG software.</p> <p>Computer codes for automatic calculation of various metrics from blood oxygen saturation and photoplethysmography signals.</p>	
	ITA	License	License for using the services providing access to the data sets (climatic data and derived data, Copernicus images and derived data, Spanish registry data - rustic parcels, etc.), transforming data set functionality, and predictions models.	5

In the following Fig. 14, we can observe how the different assets described above interact with each other and coexist in our scenario.

Fig. 14. Mapping of assets.

5.8.2. General Architecture

Below, in Fig. 15, we present an overview of the architecture that constitutes our ecosystem for accessing confidential data. We provide a global view of our infrastructure, which integrates several subsystems working together to ensure privacy and security in the handling of confidential data.

Fig. 15. General infrastructure.

Next, we will examine the functionality of each subsystem that constitutes our architecture.

- In the upper left corner, the **Verifiable Data Registry (VDR)** is located, containing trusted lists, public key storage, and revocation lists. This registry is essential for verifying credentials and managing trust within the ecosystem, ensuring that only authorized users and services interact with the data.
- The **Privacy and Security Manager Connector** serves as the core for managing user authorizations and credentials. This module is divided into two main subcomponents:
 - **Trust Usage Control Authorization (PDP-PEP)**: This subsystem functions as the authorization point for resource access. The Policy Enforcement Point (PEP) applies established policies, while the Policy Decision Point (PDP) makes decisions regarding the granting or denial of access based on these policies. This process ensures that only authorized users can access protected services.
 - **Credential Manager (SSI-Wallet)**: This component manages the user's Self-Sovereign Identity (SSI), enabling users to control their own credentials. These credentials are verified to authorize access to resources, securely stored, and used without exposing unnecessary data, thereby enhancing privacy.
- The **Protected Service** represents the service safeguarded by the privacy and security policies implemented by the Privacy and Security Manager Connector, where authentication and authorization for accessing this service are conducted under the oversight of the PDP-PEP and SSI-Wallet.
- **Confidential Data Processing** ensures that confidential data is processed securely, employing advanced technologies, including specialized hardware such as **Field-Programmable Gate Arrays (FPGA)**. FPGAs enable the efficient and customizable implementation of secure processing algorithms.
- The **Data Space Management Connector** is responsible for managing data spaces and facilitating the interaction between the data and the services that require it.
- Finally, the hardware infrastructure, which includes **Trusted Execution Environments (TEE)** and **Security Enclaves (SE)**, plays a critical role in ensuring security during operational execution. These trusted execution environments create a safe and isolated space for processing confidential data, protecting it from unauthorized access and minimizing the risk of leaks.

In summary, this architecture aims to ensure that confidential data and resources are accessed only by authorized users, maintaining high standards of privacy and security through a combination of software, self-sovereign credentials, and trusted execution environments.

5.8.3. Architecture flow

Finally, in Fig. 16, the flow followed by our ecosystem is illustrated. The process begins with the consuming user logging in (Step 1) and exchanging their Verifiable Credentials (VC) (2), which will be verified by the SSI (3). The SSI will check that the user is part of the participant list in the Verifiable Data Registry (VDR) (4). If verification is positive, an Access Token (5) will be granted, allowing the user to request data.

With the Access Token in hand, the user can request data (6). This request will be evaluated by the Policy Decision Point (PDP), which will determine whether the request is valid by

verifying compliance with the established policies (7). If the policies are met, the user will receive the requested data (8), which had previously been encrypted (0) using a public key.

Finally, upon receiving the data, the user will need to decrypt it (9). To do this, they will obtain the decryption key from the Key Authority (10), allowing them to decipher the data and access it in its original format (11).

Fig. 16. Architecture flow.

References

- [1] TITAN DoA, 'Grant Agreement No. 101129822'. 2023.
- [2] International Data Spaces Association., 'IDS-RAM 4 - International Data Spaces Reference Architecture Model version 4', IDS-RAM 4. Accessed: Oct. 24, 2024. [Online]. Available: <https://docs.internationaldataspaces.org/ids-knowledgebase/ids-ram-4>
- [3] International Data Spaces Association., 'IDSA: Driving data freedom for the whole world - The association', IDSA: Driving data freedom for the whole world - The association. Accessed: Oct. 24, 2024. [Online]. Available: <https://internationaldataspaces.org/we/the-association/>
- [4] International Data Spaces Association., 'IDSA: Driving data freedom for the whole world - Members', IDSA: Driving data freedom for the whole world - Members. Accessed: Oct. 24, 2024. [Online]. Available: <https://internationaldataspaces.org/we/members>
- [5] T. Nolden, 'Implementation of a Health Data Space with the Eclipse Dataspace Components', Bachelor's Thesis, University of Koblenz, 2023.
- [6] 'General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) – Legal Text', General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR). Accessed: Oct. 10, 2024. [Online]. Available: <https://gdpr-info.eu/>
- [7] H. Balzert, *Lehrbuch der Softwaretechnik: Basiskonzepte und Requirements Engineering*. Heidelberg: Spektrum Akademischer Verlag, 2009. doi: 10.1007/978-3-8274-2247-7.
- [8] I. Sommerville, *Software Engineering*, 10., Aktualisierte Auflage. in Informatik. Hallbergmoos/Germany: Pearson, 2018.
- [9] M. Glinz, 'A Glossary of Requirements Engineering Terminology', *Int. Requir. Eng. Board IREB*, no. 1.6, May 2014.
- [10] K. Beck, *Extreme Programming Explained - Embrace Change*. Addison - Wesley, 1999.
- [11] P. Hruschka, *Business Analysis und Requirements Engineering - Produkte und Prozesse nachhaltig verbessern*. Hanser, 2014.
- [12] W. N. Robinson, S. D. Pawlowski, and V. Volkov, 'Requirements interaction management', *ACM Comput. Surv.*, vol. 35, no. 2, pp. 132–190, Jun. 2003, doi: 10.1145/857076.857079.
- [13] P. Carlshamre, K. Sandahl, M. Lindvall, B. Regnell, and J. Natt Och Dag, 'An industrial survey of requirements interdependencies in software product release planning', in *Proceedings Fifth IEEE International Symposium on Requirements Engineering*, Toronto, ON, Canada: IEEE, 2001, pp. 84–91. doi: 10.1109/ISRE.2001.948547.
- [14] O. C. Z. Gotel and C. W. Finkelstein, 'An analysis of the requirements traceability problem', in *Proceedings of IEEE International Conference on Requirements Engineering*, Colorado Springs, CO, USA: IEEE Comput. Soc. Press, 1994, pp. 94–101. doi: 10.1109/ICRE.1994.292398.
- [15] International Standards Organization, *ISO/IEC/IEEE 24765-2010 - International Standard - Systems and software engineering -- Vocabulary*, 2010. doi: 10.1109/IEEESTD.2010.5733835.

- [16] O. Gotel *et al.*, 'Traceability Fundamentals', in *Software and Systems Traceability*, J. Cleland-Huang, O. Gotel, and A. Zisman, Eds., London: Springer London, 2012, pp. 3–22. doi: 10.1007/978-1-4471-2239-5_1.
- [17] International Standards Organization, *IEC 62304:2006 Medical device software – Software life cycle processes*, 2006. Accessed: Oct. 23, 2024. [Online]. Available: <https://www.iso.org/committee/54892.html>
- [18] S. Winkler and J. Von Pilgrim, 'A survey of traceability in requirements engineering and model-driven development', *Softw. Syst. Model.*, vol. 9, no. 4, pp. 529–565, Sep. 2010, doi: 10.1007/s10270-009-0145-0.
- [19] G. Spanoudakis and A. Zisman, 'Software Traceability: A Roadmap', in *Handbook Of Software Engineering And Knowledge Engineering*, WORLD SCIENTIFIC, 2005, pp. 395–428. doi: 10.1142/9789812775245_0014.
- [20] K. Großer, V. Riediger, and J. Jürjens, 'Requirements document relations: A reuse perspective on traceability through standards', *Softw. Syst. Model.*, vol. 21, no. 6, pp. 1–37, Dec. 2022, doi: 10.1007/s10270-021-00958-y.
- [21] Oscar Corcho *et al.*, 'EOSC Interoperability Framework (v1.0)'. May 03, 2020.
- [22] 'ISO 25010'. Accessed: Oct. 07, 2024. [Online]. Available: <https://iso25000.com/index.php/en/iso-25000-standards/iso-25010>
- [23] C. Rupp and SOPHIST GmbH, *Requirements-Engineering und -Management – Aus der Praxis von klassisch bis agil*, 7th ed. Carl Hanser Verlag München, 2020.
- [24] International Standards Organization, *ISO/IEC/IEEE 29148:2018(E) - Systems and software engineering – Life cycle processes – Requirements engineering*, 2018. doi: 10.1109/IEEESTD.2018.8559686.
- [25] ECSS European Cooperation for Space Standardization, *ECSS-E-ST-10-06C: Space engineering - Technical requirements specification*. ECSS, 2009. [Online]. Available: <https://ecss.nl/standard/ecss-e-st-10-06c-technical-requirements-specification/>
- [26] 'TANGO Public Deliverables'. Accessed: Oct. 10, 2024. [Online]. Available: <https://tango-project.eu/materials/public-deliverables>

Appendix

Technical Requirements

This section contains the current list of technical requirements. Each of the requirements is visualised in a table like the one shown in Table 6. Information that is not yet captured is not shown in the individual requirements (i.e. the rows are omitted). The legal and ethical requirements are documented in the same way in the TITAN deliverable D1.1.

Req. ID	Unique requirement identifier		
Type	Functional, Non-Functional		
Category	One of the categories from section 5.5.1		
Liability, Priority	SHALL, SHOULD, WILL	HIGH, MEDIUM, LOW	
Subject Matter	System, Sub-System, Actor		
Requirement Sentence	Sentence according to one of the templates		
Justification	Rationale that shows importance for TITAN		
Obstacles, Barriers, Risks, Conflicts	Identified problems, requirement IDs		
Author	Partner shortcut		
Responsible Tasks	Task number(s) from proposal		
Objectives / Goals	Objective numbers(s) from proposal		
Source	Stakeholder(s)		
Comments	Additional information that supports the requirement, clarifications for understandability, etc.		
Refers To	Relevant documents, references		
Acceptance Criteria, Test/Validation Method	How fulfilment is checked		
Validation Date, Status, Validated By	YYYY-MM-DD	PASS, FAIL	

Table 6. Requirement Documentation Table Template.

Functional Requirements

fun-001

Aspect	Content
Type	Functional
Category	Data Sovereignty and Control
Liability	SHALL
Priority	-
Subject Matter	Access Controls
Requirement Sentence	The system SHALL enforce role-based access control (RBAC) allowing data owners to assign specific roles to users, defining permissions for data access, modification, and sharing.
Justification	Ensures precise control over data access and modification.
Author	UKO
Refers to	Gaia-X, IDSA, DSSC

fun-002

Aspect	Content
Type	Functional
Category	Data Sovereignty and Control
Liability	SHALL
Priority	-
Subject Matter	Access Controls
Requirement Sentence	The system SHALL enforce attribute-based access control (ABAC) enabling data owners to specify access permissions based on user attributes such as department, job title, or location.
Justification	Provides flexibility in access control based on dynamic attributes.
Author	UKO
Refers to	Gaia-X, IDSA, DSSC

fun-003

Aspect	Content
Type	Functional
Category	Data Sovereignty and Control
Liability	WILL
Priority	-
Subject Matter	Consent Management
Requirement Sentence	The system WILL provide an interface for data owners to capture consent from data subjects, specifying which data processing activities are permitted.
Justification	Ensures that data processing complies with user consent, enhancing trust and legal compliance.
Author	UKO
Refers to	Gaia-X, IDSA

fun-004

Aspect	Content
Type	Functional
Category	Data Sovereignty and Control
Liability	WILL
Priority	-
Subject Matter	Consent Management
Requirement Sentence	The system WILL allow data owners to update or revoke consent preferences and ensure these changes are immediately enforced.
Justification	Maintains ongoing compliance with user preferences and legal requirements.
Author	UKO
Refers to	Gaia-X, IDSA

fun-005

Aspect	Content
Type	Functional
Category	Data Sovereignty and Control
Liability	WILL
Priority	-
Subject Matter	Decentralized Data Storage
Requirement Sentence	The system WILL enable data storage across distributed nodes close to the data owners to prevent centralization and data silos.
Justification	Enhances data sovereignty and reduces risks associated with central data repositories.
Author	UKO
Refers to	Gaia-X, EOSC-IF

fun-006

Aspect	Content
Type	Functional
Category	Data Sovereignty and Control
Liability	WILL
Priority	-
Subject Matter	Decentralized Data Storage
Requirement Sentence	The system WILL support peer-to-peer data sharing protocols to facilitate decentralized data storage and retrieval.
Justification	Facilitates decentralized data management, reducing central points of failure.
Author	UKO
Refers to	Gaia-X, EOSC-IF

fun-007

Aspect	Content
Type	Functional
Category	Data Sovereignty and Control
Liability	SHOULD
Priority	-
Subject Matter	Revocation of Data Access
Requirement Sentence	The system SHOULD provide data owners with the ability to revoke access to their data through a user-friendly interface.
Justification	Empowers data owners to maintain control over their data.
Author	UKO
Refers to	Gaia-X, IDSA

fun-008

Aspect	Content
Type	Functional
Category	Data Sovereignty and Control
Liability	SHALL
Priority	-
Subject Matter	Revocation of Data Access
Requirement Sentence	The system SHALL ensure that revoked access is propagated throughout the network in real-time, preventing unauthorized data access.
Justification	Ensures immediate enforcement of access revocation to maintain security.
Author	UKO
Refers to	Gaia-X, IDSA

fun-009

Aspect	Content
Type	Functional
Category	Interoperability and Open Standards
Liability	SHALL
Priority	-
Subject Matter	Adoption of Open Standards
Requirement Sentence	The system SHALL support data formats such as CSV, JSON, and XML to ensure compatibility with various data sources and consumers.
Justification	Facilitates interoperability and ease of data exchange across systems.
Author	UKO
Refers to	Gaia-X, IDSA, EOSC-IF

fun-010

Aspect	Content
Type	Functional
Category	Interoperability and Open Standards
Liability	WILL
Priority	-
Subject Matter	Adoption of Open Standards
Requirement Sentence	The system WILL implement APIs based on REST and GraphQL standards for seamless integration with other systems.
Justification	Promotes interoperability and ease of integration.
Author	UKO
Refers to	Gaia-X, IDSA, EOSC-IF

fun-011

Aspect	Content
Type	Functional
Category	Interoperability and Open Standards
Liability	SHALL
Priority	-
Subject Matter	Adoption of Open Standards
Requirement Sentence	The system SHALL use protocols like HTTP and MQTT for data transmission to ensure reliable and secure communication.
Justification	Ensures secure and reliable data transmission.
Author	UKO
Refers to	Gaia-X, IDSA, EOSC-IF

fun-012

Aspect	Content
Type	Functional
Category	Data Security and Privacy
Liability	SHALL
Priority	-
Subject Matter	End-to-End Encryption
Requirement Sentence	The system SHALL encrypt data at rest using AES-256 or ChaCha20-Poly1305 encryption algorithms.
Justification	Ensures strong protection of stored data.
Author	UKO
Refers to	Gaia-X, IDSA

fun-013

Aspect	Content
Type	Functional
Category	Data Security and Privacy
Liability	WILL
Priority	-
Subject Matter	End-to-End Encryption
Requirement Sentence	The system WILL encrypt data in transit using TLS 1.2 or higher to ensure secure data transmission.
Justification	Protects data during transmission from eavesdropping and tampering.
Author	UKO
Refers to	Gaia-X, IDSA

fun-014

Aspect	Content
Type	Functional
Category	Data Security and Privacy
Liability	WILL
Priority	-
Subject Matter	Secure Authentication and Identity Management
Requirement Sentence	The system WILL support OAuth 2.0 and OpenID Connect for secure user authentication.
Justification	Ensures secure and standardized user authentication.
Author	UKO
Refers to	Gaia-X, IDSA, DSSC, EOSC-IF

fun-015

Aspect	Content
Type	Functional
Category	Data Security and Privacy
Liability	WILL
Priority	-
Subject Matter	Secure Authentication and Identity Management
Requirement Sentence	The system WILL support multi-factor authentication (MFA) for all users to enhance security.
Justification	Provides an additional layer of security to prevent unauthorized access.
Author	UKO
Refers to	Gaia-X, IDSA, DSSC, EOSC-IF

fun-016

Aspect	Content
Type	Functional
Category	Data Security and Privacy
Liability	SHOULD
Priority	-
Subject Matter	Secure Authentication and Identity Management
Requirement Sentence	The system SHOULD integrate with enterprise identity providers such as LDAP and Active Directory for centralized identity management.
Justification	Enables centralized and secure management of user identities.
Author	UKO
Refers to	Gaia-X, IDSA

fun-017

Aspect	Content
Type	Functional
Category	Data Security and Privacy
Liability	SHOULD
Priority	-
Subject Matter	Transparency in Data Handling
Requirement Sentence	The system SHOULD include a feature to generate reports detailing data collection, usage, and sharing activities.
Justification	Enhances transparency and accountability in data handling.
Author	UKO
Refers to	Gaia-X

fun-018

Aspect	Content
Type	Functional
Category	Data Security and Privacy
Liability	WILL
Priority	-
Subject Matter	Transparency in Data Handling
Requirement Sentence	The system WILL provide a user interface where data subjects can view and manage their data handling preferences.
Justification	Empowers users with control over their data and increases transparency.
Author	UKO
Refers to	Gaia-X

fun-019

Aspect	Content
Type	Functional
Category	Federation and Decentralization
Liability	SHALL
Priority	-
Subject Matter	Federated Architecture
Requirement Sentence	The system SHALL implement a federated architecture where multiple independent nodes collaborate without a central controlling entity.
Justification	Ensures no single point of control, enhancing decentralization and data sovereignty.
Author	UKO
Refers to	Gaia-X, IDSA, EOSC-IF

fun-020

Aspect	Content
Type	Functional
Category	Federation and Decentralization
Liability	SHALL
Priority	-
Subject Matter	Federated Architecture
Requirement Sentence	The system SHALL use federated identity management to allow seamless user authentication across different nodes.
Justification	Facilitates seamless user authentication across a federated network.
Author	UKO
Refers to	Gaia-X, IDSA

fun-021

Aspect	Content
Type	Functional
Category	Federation and Decentralization
Liability	WILL
Priority	-
Subject Matter	Decentralized Data Processing
Requirement Sentence	The system WILL support edge computing capabilities to process data closer to its source, reducing latency and enhancing data sovereignty.
Justification	Improves performance and maintains data control closer to its origin.
Author	UKO
Refers to	Gaia-X, IDSA

fun-022

Aspect	Content
Type	Functional
Category	Federation and Decentralization
Liability	SHALL
Priority	-
Subject Matter	Decentralized Data Processing
Requirement Sentence	The system SHALL implement distributed ledger technologies to maintain a tamper-proof record of data transactions.
Justification	Ensures data integrity and transparency in transactions.
Author	UKO
Refers to	Gaia-X, IDSA

fun-023

Aspect	Content
Type	Functional
Category	Federation and Decentralization
Liability	WILL
Priority	-
Subject Matter	Multi-Party Trust Frameworks
Requirement Sentence	The system WILL include audit mechanisms to ensure all parties adhere to established trust and compliance rules.
Justification	Ensures accountability and compliance with trust frameworks.
Author	UKO
Refers to	Gaia-X, IDSA

fun-024

Aspect	Content
Type	Functional
Category	Transparency and Open Governance
Liability	SHOULD
Priority	-
Subject Matter	Transparent Policies and Decision-Making
Requirement Sentence	The system SHOULD implement a feedback mechanism for stakeholders to provide input on governance and operational decisions.
Justification	Facilitates stakeholder engagement and continuous improvement.
Author	UKO
Refers to	Gaia-X, IDSA

fun-025

Aspect	Content
Type	Functional
Category	Transparency and Open Governance
Liability	WILL
Priority	-
Subject Matter	Transparent Policies and Decision-Making
Requirement Sentence	The system WILL support automated data lifecycle management, including data archiving and deletion based on predefined policies.
Justification	Facilitates efficient data management and compliance with data retention policies.
Author	UKO
Refers to	Gaia-X, IDSA, EOSC-IF

fun-026

Aspect	Content
Type	Functional
Category	Transparency and Open Governance
Liability	SHOULD
Priority	-
Subject Matter	Involvement of Diverse Stakeholders
Requirement Sentence	The system SHOULD establish working groups and committees inclusive of industry, academia, and government representatives.
Justification	Ensures diverse perspectives and expertise in decision-making.
Author	UKO
Refers to	Gaia-X, IDSA

fun-027

Aspect	Content
Type	Functional
Category	Transparency and Open Governance
Liability	SHOULD
Priority	-
Subject Matter	Involvement of Diverse Stakeholders
Requirement Sentence	The system SHOULD hold regular meetings and consultations with stakeholders to gather feedback and ensure the ecosystem meets diverse needs.
Justification	Promotes ongoing stakeholder involvement and responsiveness to needs.
Author	UKO
Refers to	Gaia-X, IDSA

fun-028

Aspect	Content
Type	Functional
Category	Common Building Blocks and Blueprint
Liability	SHALL
Priority	-
Subject Matter	Data Spaces Blueprint
Requirement Sentence	The system SHALL develop a "Data Spaces Blueprint" document providing detailed guidelines on business, legal, operational, technical, and societal aspects of data spaces.
Justification	Provides comprehensive guidelines to ensure successful implementation and operation of data spaces.
Author	UKO
Refers to	DSSC, EOSC-IF

fun-029

Aspect	Content
Type	Functional
Category	Common Building Blocks and Blueprint
Liability	SHALL
Priority	-
Subject Matter	Data Spaces Blueprint
Requirement Sentence	The system SHALL include reusable components and templates in the blueprint to facilitate the setup and management of data spaces.
Justification	Simplifies and standardizes the creation and management of data spaces.
Author	UKO
Refers to	DSSC, EOSC-IF

fun-030

Aspect	Content
Type	Functional
Category	User-Centric Approach
Liability	WILL
Priority	-
Subject Matter	Stakeholder Feedback Integration
Requirement Sentence	The system WILL include a feature to collect and analyse stakeholder feedback continuously.
Justification	Ensures the system remains user-centric and responsive to stakeholder needs.
Author	UKO
Refers to	Gaia-X, IDSA, DSSC

fun-031

Aspect	Content
Type	Functional
Category	User-Centric Approach
Liability	SHOULD
Priority	-
Subject Matter	Stakeholder Feedback Integration
Requirement Sentence	The system SHOULD provide regular updates and improvements based on stakeholder feedback to ensure the ecosystem remains user centric.
Justification	Promotes ongoing adaptation and improvement based on user needs.
Author	UKO
Refers to	DSSC

fun-032

Aspect	Content
Type	Functional
Category	Catalogues and Metadata Management
Liability	SHALL
Priority	-
Subject Matter	Metadata Catalogues
Requirement Sentence	The system SHALL implement metadata catalogues that allow users to annotate and search data assets.
Justification	Enhances data discoverability and usability.
Author	UKO
Refers to	Gaia-X, IDSA, DSSC, EOSC-IF

fun-033

Aspect	Content
Type	Functional
Category	Catalogues and Metadata Management
Liability	SHOULD
Priority	-
Subject Matter	Metadata Catalogues
Requirement Sentence	The system SHOULD include automated metadata extraction and classification tools to enhance discoverability.
Justification	Improves the accuracy and efficiency of metadata management.
Author	UKO
Refers to	Gaia-X, IDSA, DSSC, EOSC-IF

fun-034

Aspect	Content
Type	Functional
Category	Catalogues and Metadata Management
Liability	WILL
Priority	-
Subject Matter	Federated Catalog Searches
Requirement Sentence	The system WILL support federated search functionality, enabling users to query across multiple decentralized catalogues.
Justification	Facilitates comprehensive data discovery across decentralized sources.
Author	UKO
Refers to	IDSA, DSSC

fun-035

Aspect	Content
Type	Functional
Category	Catalogues and Metadata Management
Liability	SHALL
Priority	-
Subject Matter	Federated Catalog Searches
Requirement Sentence	The system SHALL implement advanced search filters and ranking algorithms to improve the relevance of search results.
Justification	Enhances user experience by providing more relevant search results.
Author	UKO
Refers to	IDSA, DSSC, EOSC-IF

fun-036

Aspect	Content
Type	Functional
Category	Catalogues and Metadata Management
Liability	SHOULD
Priority	-
Subject Matter	Agreed Vocabularies and Access Controls
Requirement Sentence	The system SHOULD establish standardized vocabularies for metadata to ensure consistent interpretation across different systems.
Justification	Promotes consistency and accuracy in metadata usage.
Author	UKO
Refers to	Gaia-X, IDSA, DSSC, EOSC-IF

fun-037

Aspect	Content
Type	Functional
Category	Catalogues and Metadata Management
Liability	SHALL
Priority	-
Subject Matter	Agreed Vocabularies and Access Controls
Requirement Sentence	The system SHALL implement access control mechanisms for metadata catalogues to ensure secure and authorized access.
Justification	Protects metadata from unauthorized access and ensures proper usage.
Author	UKO
Refers to	Gaia-X, IDSA, DSSC

fun-038

Aspect	Content
Type	Functional
Category	Data Sharing Capabilities
Liability	SHOULD
Priority	-
Subject Matter	Negotiation and Establishment of Data Contracts
Requirement Sentence	The system SHOULD provide a user interface for participants to negotiate data contracts, specifying terms, conditions, and usage rights.
Justification	Facilitates clear and enforceable agreements between data providers and consumers.
Author	UKO
Refers to	IDSA

fun-039

Aspect	Content
Type	Functional
Category	Data Sharing Capabilities
Liability	SHALL
Priority	-
Subject Matter	Negotiation and Establishment of Data Contracts
Requirement Sentence	The system SHALL store and manage data contracts securely, ensuring they are enforceable and auditable.
Justification	Ensures the integrity and enforceability of data sharing agreements.
Author	UKO
Refers to	IDSA

fun-040

Aspect	Content
Type	Functional
Category	Data Sharing Capabilities
Liability	SHALL
Priority	-
Subject Matter	Enforcement of Data Provider Policies
Requirement Sentence	The system SHALL implement mechanisms to enforce data provider policies during data sharing, ensuring compliance with agreed terms.
Justification	Ensures data is used according to provider specifications, maintaining trust.
Author	UKO
Refers to	IDSA, DSSC, EOSC-IF

fun-041

Aspect	Content
Type	Functional
Category	Data Sharing Capabilities
Liability	SHOULD
Priority	-
Subject Matter	Enforcement of Data Provider Policies
Requirement Sentence	The system SHOULD include monitoring tools to track data usage and detect policy violations.
Justification	Ensures compliance with data usage policies and enables quick detection of violations.
Author	UKO
Refers to	IDSA, DSSC, EOSC-IF

fun-042

Aspect	Content
Type	Functional
Category	Data Sharing Capabilities
Liability	WILL
Priority	-
Subject Matter	Support for Peer-to-Peer and Collective Data Services
Requirement Sentence	The system WILL support peer-to-peer data exchange protocols for direct data sharing between participants.
Justification	Facilitates flexible and direct data sharing without intermediaries.
Author	UKO
Refers to	IDSA

fun-043

Aspect	Content
Type	Functional
Category	Data Sharing Capabilities
Liability	SHOULD
Priority	-
Subject Matter	Support for Peer-to-Peer and Collective Data Services
Requirement Sentence	The system SHOULD enable collective data services, allowing groups of participants to collaboratively share and use data.
Justification	Enhances collaborative data use and value creation.
Author	UKO
Refers to	IDSA, EOSC-IF

fun-044

Aspect	Content
Type	Functional
Category	Personal Data Handling
Liability	SHALL
Priority	-
Subject Matter	Guidelines for Personal Data Handling
Requirement Sentence	The system SHALL include training materials and best practices for users handling personal data.
Justification	Educates users on compliant and effective personal data management.
Author	UKO
Refers to	IDSA, EOSC-IF

fun-045

Aspect	Content
Type	Functional
Category	Personal Data Handling
Liability	SHOULD
Priority	-
Subject Matter	Data Sovereignty for Individuals
Requirement Sentence	The system SHOULD provide individuals with tools to control how their personal data is collected, used, and shared.
Justification	Empowers individuals with control over their personal data, enhancing trust and compliance.
Author	UKO
Refers to	IDSA

fun-046

Aspect	Content
Type	Functional
Category	Personal Data Handling
Liability	SHOULD
Priority	-
Subject Matter	Data Sovereignty for Individuals
Requirement Sentence	The system SHOULD implement features that allow individuals to grant, revoke, and manage consent for data processing activities.
Justification	Ensures ongoing compliance with individual data preferences and legal requirements.
Author	UKO
Refers to	IDSA

fun-047

Aspect	Content
Type	Functional
Category	Data Resilience
Liability	SHALL
Priority	-
Subject Matter	Data Recovery
Requirement Sentence	The system SHALL provide data backup and recovery mechanisms to prevent data loss.
Justification	Ensures data availability and resilience in case of hardware failures or other disasters.
Author	UKO
Refers to	Gaia-X

fun-048

Aspect	Content
Type	Functional
Category	Data Resilience
Liability	SHALL
Priority	-
Subject Matter	Data Recovery
Requirement Sentence	The system SHALL implement regular data backups to prevent data loss and ensure data recovery in case of failure.
Justification	Ensures data availability and resilience against data loss.
Author	UKO
Refers to	Gaia-X

fun-049

Aspect	Content
Type	Functional
Category	Data Resilience
Liability	SHOULD
Priority	-
Subject Matter	Data Recovery
Requirement Sentence	The Recovery Point Objective (RPO) for the product SHOULD be 0 for a single and multiple instance(s).
Justification	Minimizes data loss during system failures
Author	UKO
Refers to	Gaia-X

fun-050

Aspect	Content
Type	Functional
Category	Data Resilience
Liability	SHOULD
Priority	-
Subject Matter	Data Recovery
Requirement Sentence	The RTO for the product SHOULD be one Minute for a single instance. For multiple instances the RTO SHOULD be 0.
Justification	Minimizes data loss during system failures
Author	UKO
Refers to	Gaia-X

fun-051

Aspect	Content
Type	Functional
Category	Data Resilience
Liability	SHALL
Priority	-
Subject Matter	Service Continuity
Requirement Sentence	The system SHALL support failover mechanisms to switch to a standby system in case of primary system failure.
Justification	Ensures service continuity and minimizes downtime during system failures.
Author	UKO
Refers to	Gaia-X

fun-052

Aspect	Content
Type	Functional
Category	Data Resilience
Liability	SHALL
Priority	-
Subject Matter	Service Continuity
Requirement Sentence	Critical components in the system SHALL be identified and strategies to warranty their availability and scalability SHALL be implemented.
Justification	Ensures service availability and minimizes downtime during system failures.
Author	UKO
Refers to	Gaia-X

fun-053

Aspect	Content
Type	Functional
Category	Authentication & Authorization
Liability	SHALL
Priority	HIGH
Subject Matter	System
Requirement Sentence	The system SHALL apply an authentication and authorisation solution that could be federated.
Justification	Authentication and authorisation often need to be performed separately for each community/service but at the same time allow interoperability.
Author	UMU
Responsible Task(s)	Task 2.1
Refers to	Architecture WG Authentication and Authorization Infrastructure (AAI) principles

fun-054

Aspect	Content
Type	Functional
Category	Feature
Liability	SHOULD
Priority	MEDIUM
Subject Matter	System
Requirement Sentence	The system SHOULD BE ABLE TO maintain a repository of semantic artefacts, and a governance framework for such a repository.
Justification	Not only data should be considered in this context, but also this should be extensible to other types of resources used in science, such as software, methods, scientific workflows, laboratory protocols, hardware designs, etc.
Author	UMU
Responsible Task(s)	Task 2.2
Refers to	EOSC IF

fun-055

Aspect	Content
Type	Functional
Category	Security & Privacy
Liability	SHALL
Priority	HIGH
Subject Matter	System
Requirement Sentence	The system SHALL BE ABLE TO apply fine-grained control over data access and usage control.
Justification	Allows to have great control over data sharing.
Author	UMU
Responsible Task(s)	Task 2.1
Refers to	TANGO D2.3: https://tango-project.eu/materials/public-deliverables

fun-056

Aspect	Content
Type	Functional
Category	Security & Privacy
Liability	SHALL
Priority	MEDIUM
Subject Matter	dp-ABC Cryptographic System
Requirement Sentence	The dp-ABC cryptographic system SHALL BE ABLE TO generate and manage private and public keys for signing.
Justification	The dp-ABC cryptography gives users granular control over the amount of personal information revealed about them and needs specific steps to manage the necessary material.
Author	UMU
Responsible Task(s)	Task 2.1
Refers to	TANGO D2.3: https://tango-project.eu/materials/public-deliverables

fun-057

Aspect	Content
Type	Functional
Category	Authentication & Authorization
Liability	SHALL
Priority	MEDIUM
Subject Matter	Authentication System
Requirement Sentence	The authentication system SHALL PROVIDE the users WITH THE ABILITY TO choose the specific data that will be shared during an authentication and authorization process.
Justification	The authentication/authorization system will be fine-grained, allowing data minimization, and users must consent to which data will be shared.
Author	UMU
Responsible Task(s)	Task 2.1

fun-058

Aspect	Content
Type	Functional
Category	Security & Authentication
Liability	SHALL
Priority	HIGH
Subject Matter	System
Requirement Sentence	The system SHALL ensure that access to data is restricted to authorized users only.
Justification	Restricting access to authorized users helps to safeguard sensitive data, ensuring that only those with the necessary permissions can access it. This minimizes the risk of data breaches or misuse by unauthorized individuals.
Author	UMU
Responsible Task(s)	Task 2.1
Refers to	EHDS

fun-059

Aspect	Content
Type	Functional
Category	Data Privacy
Liability	SHALL
Priority	MEDIUM
Subject Matter	System
Requirement Sentence	The system SHALL prohibit the downloading of personal data from the secure processing environment.
Justification	Preventing data downloads ensures sensitive information stays within the secure environment, reducing risks of leaks.
Author	UMU
Responsible Task(s)	Task 2.1
Refers to	EHDS

fun-060

Aspect	Content
Type	Functional
Category	Data Privacy
Liability	SHALL
Priority	MEDIUM
Subject Matter	System
Requirement Sentence	The system SHALL allow only the extraction of aggregated results and fully anonymized data.
Justification	Allowing only aggregated or fully anonymized data to be extracted ensures that personal identities are protected.
Author	UMU
Responsible Task(s)	Task 2.1
Refers to	EHDS

fun-061

Aspect	Content
Type	Functional
Category	Non-linear operations
Liability	SHALL
Priority	HIGH
Subject Matter	Trusted Execution Environment
Requirement Sentence	The Trusted Execution Environment SHALL BE ABLE TO support arbitrary operations on data.
Justification	Required to perform analyses and support ML operations.
Author	UEF
Responsible Task(s)	Task 7.2
Refers to	N/A

fun-062

Aspect	Content
Type	Functional
Category	Non-linear operations
Liability	SHALL
Priority	HIGH
Subject Matter	Trusted Execution Environment
Requirement Sentence	The Trusted Execution Environment SHALL BE ABLE TO support arbitrary programming languages.
Justification	Required to perform analyses and support ML operations.
Author	UEF
Responsible Task(s)	Task 7.2
Refers to	N/A

fun-063

Aspect	Content
Type	Functional
Category	Non-linear operations
Liability	SHALL
Priority	HIGH
Subject Matter	Trusted Execution Environment
Requirement Sentence	The Trusted Execution Environment SHALL BE ABLE TO support arbitrary programming packages.
Justification	Required to perform analyses and support ML operations.
Author	UEF
Responsible Task(s)	Task 7.2
Refers to	N/A

fun-064

Aspect	Content
Type	Functional
Category	Efficiency
Liability	SHOULD
Priority	MEDIUM
Subject Matter	Trusted Execution Environment
Requirement Sentence	The Trusted Execution Environment SHOULD BE ABLE TO support GPU accelerated computing.
Justification	Would be nice to have fast computation.
Author	UEF
Responsible Task(s)	Task 4.1
Refers to	N/A

fun-065

Aspect	Content
Type	Functional
Category	Security & Maintainability
Liability	SHALL
Priority	HIGH
Subject Matter	Trusted Execution Environment
Requirement Sentence	The Trusted Execution Environment SHALL BE ABLE TO control the access to data on a user-by-user basis.
Justification	Not all users need access to all data.
Author	UEF
Responsible Task(s)	Task 4.1
Refers to	N/A

fun-066

Aspect	Content
Type	Functional
Category	Security & Privacy
Liability	SHALL
Priority	MEDIUM
Subject Matter	Trusted Execution Environment
Requirement Sentence	The Trusted Execution Environment SHALL BE ABLE TO support the access from closed hospital systems.
Justification	Users need to use the system from these places.
Author	UEF
Responsible Task(s)	Task 4.1
Refers to	N/A

fun-067

Aspect	Content
Type	Functional
Category	Security & Privacy
Liability	SHALL
Priority	HIGH
Subject Matter	Trusted Execution Environment
Requirement Sentence	The Trusted Execution Environment SHALL PROVIDE the users WITH THE ABILITY TO track the usage of their data and models.
Justification	Mitigates misuse of data.
Author	UEF
Responsible Task(s)	Task 4.1
Refers to	N/A

fun-068

Aspect	Content
Type	Functional
Category	Usability
Liability	SHOULD
Priority	MEDIUM
Subject Matter	Trusted Execution Environment
Requirement Sentence	The Trusted Execution Environment SHOULD have a Graphical User Interface (UI).
Justification	If usability is low, few partners will use the system.
Author	UEF
Responsible Task(s)	Task 4.1
Refers to	N/A

fun-069

Aspect	Content
Type	Functional
Category	Monitoring & Traceability
Liability	SHOULD
Priority	LOW
Subject Matter	Audit System
Requirement Sentence	The Audit System SHOULD BE ABLE TO log system information and actions.
Justification	For security monitoring purposes, stored in a persistent environment.
Author	FRA
Refers to	N/A

fun-070

Aspect	Content
Type	Functional
Category	Data Discovery
Liability	SHOULD
Priority	MEDIUM
Subject Matter	Data Sharing Platform
Requirement Sentence	The Data Sharing Platform SHOULD BE ABLE TO provide tools to handle metadata and vocabulary transparently.
Justification	This facilitates standardization and supports data discovery.
Author	FRA
Refers to	GAIA-X, IDSA, DSSC

fun-071

Aspect	Content
Type	Functional
Category	Data Sharing
Liability	SHALL
Priority	HIGH
Subject Matter	Data Sharing Platform
Requirement Sentence	The Data Sharing Platform SHALL PROVIDE authorized end users WITH THE ABILITY to download data.
Justification	Key feature for data sharing.
Author	FRA
Refers to	GAIA-X, IDSA, DSSC

fun-072

Aspect	Content
Type	Functional
Category	Data Sharing
Liability	SHOULD
Priority	MEDIUM
Subject Matter	Data Sharing Platform
Requirement Sentence	The Data Sharing Platform SHOULD PROVIDE authorized end users WITH THE ABILITY to access real time/streaming data in a controlled way.
Justification	Minor feature for data sharing.
Author	FRA
Refers to	GAIA-X, IDSA, DSSC

fun-073

Aspect	Content
Type	Functional
Category	Data Sharing
Liability	SHOULD
Priority	LOW
Subject Matter	Data Sharing Platform
Requirement Sentence	The Data Sharing Platform SHOULD BE ABLE TO process real time and near real time data.
Justification	Minor feature for data sharing.
Author	FRA
Refers to	GAIA-X, IDSA, DSSC

fun-074

Aspect	Content
Type	Functional
Category	Authentication & Authorization
Liability	SHALL
Priority	HIGH
Subject Matter	Data Sharing Platform
Requirement Sentence	The Data Sharing Platform SHALL BE ABLE TO handle the authorisation of end users by enforcing the access rights policies.
Justification	Key feature for data sharing.
Author	FRA
Refers to	GAIA-X, IDSA, DSSC

fun-075

Aspect	Content
Type	Functional
Category	Data Discovery
Liability	SHALL
Priority	HIGH
Subject Matter	Data Sharing Platform
Requirement Sentence	The Data Sharing Platform SHALL provide catalog and resource discovery services.
Justification	This supports the search functionality.
Author	FRA
Refers to	GAIA-X, IDSA, DSSC

fun-076

Aspect	Content
Type	Functional
Category	Authentication & Authorization
Liability	SHALL
Priority	HIGH
Subject Matter	Authentication Platform
Requirement Sentence	The Authentication Platform SHALL BE ABLE TO enable users to have control of their identity.
Justification	Users have control of their identity, to protect their rights based on EU regulations, and increase the sense of security and transparency.
Author	FRA
Refers to	GAIA-X, IDSA, DSSC

fun-077

Aspect	Content
Type	Functional
Category	Authentication & Authorization
Liability	SHALL
Priority	HIGH
Subject Matter	Authentication Platform
Requirement Sentence	The Authentication Platform SHALL BE ABLE TO enable users to have control of the data they provide to the platform.
Justification	Users have control of the data they provide to the platform, to protect their rights based on EU regulations, and increase the sense of security and transparency.
Author	FRA
Refers to	GAIA-X, IDSA, DSSC

fun-078

Aspect	Content
Type	Functional
Category	Security & Maintainability
Liability	SHALL
Priority	HIGH
Subject Matter	System
Requirement Sentence	The system SHALL BE ABLE TO manage and store fine-grained data access control policies in a decentralized manner, based on a distributed ledger.
Justification	Enables the data owners to define fine-grained access control and applies it throughout the network without centralized administration.
Author	ZEN
Responsible Task(s)	Task 3.2

fun-079

Aspect	Content
Type	Functional
Category	Security & Maintainability
Liability	SHALL
Priority	HIGH
Subject Matter	System
Requirement Sentence	The system SHALL implement decentralized identities for data access authorization.
Justification	Enabling persistent unique identification of involved parties and other entities (devices, assets) in a decentralized manner.
Author	ZEN
Responsible Task(s)	Task 3.2

fun-080

Aspect	Content
Type	Functional
Category	Federated Learning
Liability	SHALL
Priority	HIGH
Subject Matter	Federated Learning Toolbox
Requirement Sentence	The Federated Learning Toolbox SHALL enable secure orchestration (deployment and aggregation) of Federated Learning workloads.
Justification	Essential baseline functionality for the FL support.
Author	ZEN
Responsible Task(s)	T5.1

fun-081

Aspect	Content
Type	Functional
Category	Federated Learning
Liability	SHALL
Priority	HIGH
Subject Matter	Federated Learning Toolbox
Requirement Sentence	The Federated Learning Toolbox SHALL enable collaborative multi-party data analysis supporting machine learning without central posting of the datasets, using a secure server and nodes cloud infrastructure.
Justification	Essential baseline functionality of the FL, decoupling private data from the learning algorithms execution and model training.
Author	ZEN
Responsible Task(s)	T5.1, T5.2

fun-082

Aspect	Content
Type	Functional
Category	Monitoring & Traceability
Liability	SHALL
Priority	MEDIUM
Subject Matter	Audit System
Requirement Sentence	The Audit System SHALL BE ABLE to store log files.
Justification	Troubleshooting and performance monitoring, as well as ensuring security, compliance, and incident response. They provide essential audit trails for tracking system activities and changes.
Author	FUJ
Responsible Task(s)	Task 2.1
Refers to	NIST CSF (ID,AM-5)

fun-083

Aspect	Content
Type	Functional
Category	Monitoring & Traceability
Liability	SHALL
Priority	MEDIUM
Subject Matter	Audit System
Requirement Sentence	The Audit System SHALL BE ABLE to access log files.
Justification	Troubleshooting and performance monitoring, as well as ensuring security, compliance, and incident response. They provide essential audit trails for tracking system activities and changes.
Author	FUJ
Responsible Task(s)	Task 2.1
Refers to	NIST CSF (ID,AM-5)

fun-084

Aspect	Content
Type	Functional
Category	Monitoring & Traceability
Liability	SHALL
Priority	MEDIUM
Subject Matter	Audit System
Requirement Sentence	Depending on the architecture, the Audit System SHALL BE ABLE to have centralized/decentralized log management solutions to store and analyse log data for threat detection and incident response.
Justification	Decentralized/Centralized log management solutions are essential for storing and analysing log data to enhance threat detection and incident response, providing a unified platform for monitoring, alerting, and investigating security events efficiently.
Author	FUJ
Responsible Task(s)	Task 2.1
Refers to	NIST CSF (ID,AM-5) (PR,DS-6 PR,DS-8) (DE,CM-1 2 3) (RS-AN-1 2 3) (RC,IM-1)

fun-085

Aspect	Content
Type	Functional
Category	User Interface
Liability	SHALL
Priority	MEDIUM
Subject Matter	Data Agreement Management Platform
Requirement Sentence	The Data Agreement Management Platform SHALL have a UI.
Justification	For facilitating collaborations across multi-disciplinary partners.
Author	FUJ
Responsible Task(s)	Task 2.1
Refers to	GDPR (Article 5(1)(a)) (Article 5(1)(c)) Article 32 Article 25

fun-086

Aspect	Content
Type	Functional
Category	User Interface
Liability	SHALL
Priority	MEDIUM
Subject Matter	Data Agreement Management Platform
Requirement Sentence	The UI of the Data Agreement Management Platform SHALL BE ABLE TO create data agreements between data providers and consumers.
Justification	For creating data agreements between data providers and consumers.
Author	FUJ
Responsible Task(s)	Task 2.1
Refers to	GDPR (Article 5(1)(a)) (Article 5(1)(c)) Article 32 Article 25

fun-087

Aspect	Content
Type	Functional
Category	Data Agreement
Liability	SHALL
Priority	MEDIUM
Subject Matter	Data Agreement Management Platform
Requirement Sentence	The Data Agreement Management Platform SHALL provide a backend side such as a NoSQL database with REST API.
Justification	For creating data agreements between data providers and consumers.
Author	FUJ
Responsible Task(s)	Task 2.1
Refers to	GDPR (Article 5(1)(a)) and data subject rights (Articles 12-23).

fun-088

Aspect	Content
Type	Functional
Category	Data Agreement
Liability	SHALL
Priority	MEDIUM
Subject Matter	Data Agreement Management Platform
Requirement Sentence	The Data Agreement Management Platform SHALL BE ABLE to provide a monitoring tool for showing the data agreements, their status (signed/accepted), updated.
Author	FUJ
Responsible Task(s)	Task 2.1
Refers to	GDPR (Article 5(1)(a)) and data subject rights (Articles 12-23).

fun-089

Aspect	Content
Type	Functional
Category	Security & Privacy
Liability	SHALL
Priority	MEDIUM
Subject Matter	Data Sharing Platform
Requirement Sentence	The Data Sharing Platform SHALL BE ABLE TO deliver enhanced anonymization and encryption capabilities.
Author	FUJ
Responsible Task(s)	Task 2.3
Refers to	GDPR Recital 26 and Article 32

fun-090

Aspect	Content
Type	Functional
Category	Security & Privacy
Liability	SHALL
Priority	MEDIUM
Subject Matter	System
Requirement Sentence	The system SHALL BE ABLE TO provide anonymisation assessment capabilities.
Justification	Enabling the evaluation of anonymized data quality while maintaining privacy.
Author	FUJ
Responsible Task(s)	Task 2.3
Refers to	NIST CSF (ID, RA-3) (PR,AC-1 4); GDPR Recital 26, Article 5(1)(a), Article 25 32 35

fun-091

Aspect	Content
Type	Functional
Category	Authentication & Authorization
Liability	SHALL
Priority	MEDIUM
Subject Matter	System
Requirement Sentence	The system SHALL BE ABLE TO maintain access to the blockchain network.
Author	FUJ
Responsible Task(s)	Task 2.2
Refers to	NIST CSF (PR, AC-1 3) (PR, ID-2)

fun-092

Aspect	Content
Type	Functional
Category	Monitoring & Traceability
Liability	SHALL
Priority	HIGH
Subject Matter	System
Requirement Sentence	The system SHALL BE ABLE TO reliably record the identity of software processing data shared by third parties.
Justification	Ensuring traceability of the version and configuration of software processing data is a cornerstone for digital trust and an enabler for digital collaboration
Author	CAB
Responsible Task(s)	Task 4.2
Source	Security Experts
Comments	N/A

fun-093

Aspect	Content
Type	Functional
Category	Security & Privacy
Liability	SHALL
Priority	HIGH
Subject Matter	System
Requirement Sentence	The system SHALL BE ABLE TO configure the access to data shared by third parties according to a policy based on the identity of the software.
Justification	Being able to define policies that reliably control and enforce software access to data helps improve scalability, traceability, and security.
Author	CAB
Responsible Task(s)	Task 4.2
Source	Security Experts
Comments	N/A

fun-094

Aspect	Content
Type	Functional
Category	Data Sharing
Liability	SHALL
Priority	-
Subject Matter	Metadata Catalog
Requirement Sentence	The Metadata Catalog SHALL BE ABLE TO assign unique and persistent identifiers to all datasets deposited.
Justification	FAIR Findability
Author	TRI
Refers to	FAIR F1 & R1

fun-095

Aspect	Content
Type	Functional
Category	Data Quality
Liability	SHALL
Priority	-
Subject Matter	Metadata Catalog
Requirement Sentence	The Metadata Catalog SHALL BE ABLE TO require comprehensive metadata submission following established vocabularies and ontologies.
Justification	FAIR Findability/Reusability
Author	TRI
Refers to	FAIR F2

fun-096

Aspect	Content
Type	Functional
Category	Data Quality
Liability	SHALL
Priority	-
Subject Matter	Metadata Catalog
Requirement Sentence	The Metadata Catalog SHALL BE ABLE TO include the identifier of the data inside the metadata they describe.
Justification	FAIR Findability
Author	TRI
Refers to	FAIR F3

fun-097

Aspect	Content
Type	Functional
Category	Data Sharing
Liability	SHALL
Priority	-
Subject Matter	Metadata Catalog
Requirement Sentence	The Metadata Catalog SHALL PROVIDE the end users WITH THE ABILITY TO search metadata.
Justification	FAIR Findability
Author	TRI
Refers to	FAIR F4

fun-098

Aspect	Content
Type	Functional
Category	Data Sharing
Liability	SHALL
Priority	-
Subject Matter	Metadata Catalog
Requirement Sentence	The Metadata Catalog SHALL PROVIDE the end users WITH THE ABILITY TO retrieve (meta)data by an identifier using a standardised communication protocol that is open, free, and universally implementable.
Justification	FAIR Accessibility
Author	TRI
Refers to	FAIR A1, A1.1

fun-099

Aspect	Content
Type	Functional
Category	Authentication & Authorization
Liability	SHALL
Priority	-
Subject Matter	Data Sharing Platform
Requirement Sentence	The Data Sharing Platform SHALL provide mechanisms for authentication and authorisation to control access to sensitive data.
Justification	FAIR Accessibility
Author	TRI
Refers to	FAIR A1.2

fun-100

Aspect	Content
Type	Functional
Category	Monitoring & Traceability
Liability	SHALL
Priority	-
Subject Matter	Data Sharing Platform
Requirement Sentence	The Data Sharing Platform SHALL BE ABLE TO persist metadata even if the data is deleted.
Justification	FAIR Accessibility
Author	TRI
Refers to	FAIR A2

fun-101

Aspect	Content
Type	Functional
Category	-
Liability	-
Priority	-
Subject Matter	Data
Requirement Sentence	Level-1C multi-spectral imaging products from the Sentinel-2 or NDVI derived products
Justification	Required to create ML models
Author	SAR
Source	Copernicus
Comments	Anomaly and change detection, yield loss, field user recommendation, spraying recommendation. The system will use multispectral remote sensing instruments on satellite at field scale. Access to data is based on a principle of full, open, and free access as established by the Copernicus data and information policy Regulation (EU) No 1159/2013 of 12 July 2013

fun-102

Aspect	Content
Type	Functional
Category	-
Liability	-
Priority	-
Subject Matter	System
Requirement Sentence	Accountability of use of data/processes
Author	SAR
Source	SARGA/ITA

Non-Functional Requirements

nfn-001

Aspect	Content
Type	Non-Functional
Category	Interoperability and Open Standards
Liability	SHALL
Priority	-
Subject Matter	Avoidance of Vendor Lock-in
Requirement Sentence	The system SHALL be built using open-source components to enable customization and avoid dependence on proprietary solutions.
Justification	Enhances flexibility, reduces costs, and avoids vendor lock-in.
Author	UKO
Refers to	Gaia-X, EOSC-IF

nfn-002

Aspect	Content
Type	Non-Functional
Category	Interoperability and Open Standards
Liability	WILL
Priority	-
Subject Matter	Avoidance of Vendor Lock-in
Requirement Sentence	The system WILL utilize modular architecture, allowing the replacement of individual components without affecting the overall system functionality.
Justification	Enhances system flexibility and ease of maintenance.
Author	UKO
Refers to	Gaia-X

nfn-003

Aspect	Content
Type	Non-Functional
Category	Transparency and Open Governance
Liability	WILL
Priority	-
Subject Matter	Open-Source Development
Requirement Sentence	The system WILL develop core components and services using open-source principles to foster transparency, collaboration, and innovation.
Justification	Encourages community involvement and continuous improvement through open-source development.
Author	UKO
Refers to	Gaia-X, IDSA

nfn-004

Aspect	Content
Type	Non-Functional
Category	Personal Data Handling
Liability	SHOULD
Priority	-
Subject Matter	Monetization Opportunities for Personal Data
Requirement Sentence	The system SHOULD explore and implement mechanisms that enable individuals to monetize their personal data securely and transparently.
Justification	Provides individuals with opportunities to benefit economically from their data while maintaining privacy and control.
Author	UKO
Refers to	IDSA

nfn-005

Aspect	Content
Type	Non-Functional
Category	Personal Data Handling
Liability	SHOULD
Priority	-
Subject Matter	Monetization Opportunities for Personal Data
Requirement Sentence	The system SHOULD provide a marketplace interface where individuals can offer their data for specific purposes and receive compensation.
Justification	Facilitates a transparent and user-controlled environment for data monetization.
Author	UKO
Refers to	IDSA

nfn-006

Aspect	Content
Type	Non-Functional
Category	Interoperability
Liability	SHOULD
Priority	MEDIUM
Subject Matter	Software components/services
Requirement Sentence	The software components/services SHOULD expose open, easily manageable, and secure APIs (e.g., RESTful APIs over HTTPS) to ensure interoperability with other components/services.
Justification	The need to facilitate interoperability requires defined on common interfaces.
Author	UMU
Responsible Task(s)	Task 2.1
Refers to	TANGO D2.3: https://tango-project.eu/materials/public-deliverables

nfn-007

Aspect	Content
Type	Non-Functional
Category	Efficiency
Liability	SHALL
Priority	MEDIUM
Subject Matter	System
Requirement Sentence	The system SHALL be highly available and fault-tolerant to avoid single points of failure.
Justification	Reliability of the solution.
Author	UMU
Responsible Task(s)	Task 4.1
Refers to	TANGO D2.3: https://tango-project.eu/materials/public-deliverables

nfn-008

Aspect	Content
Type	Non-Functional
Category	Security & Privacy
Liability	SHOULD
Priority	LOW
Subject Matter	dp-ABC Cryptographic System
Requirement Sentence	The dp-ABC cryptographic system SHOULD enable distributed issuance processes, through the aggregation of public keys and combination of signatures into one.
Justification	Distributed issuance mitigates single point of failure.
Author	UMU
Responsible Task(s)	Task 2.1
Refers to	TANGO D2.3: https://tango-project.eu/materials/public-deliverables

nfn-009

Aspect	Content
Type	Non-Functional
Category	Security & Privacy
Liability	SHOULD
Priority	MEDIUM
Subject Matter	Authentication System
Requirement Sentence	The authentication system SHOULD BE ABLE TO provide formal guarantees of Trusted Execution Environments against leaking further data than required by the user.
Justification	The technology used for authentication should ensure that the authentication process does not leak any additional data than required by the user, e.g., enabling unlikability.
Author	UMU
Responsible Task(s)	Task 2.1
Refers to	GDPR (Article 5(1)(a)) (Article 5(1)(c))

nfn-010

Aspect	Content
Type	Non-Functional
Category	Interoperability
Liability	SHOULD
Priority	MEDIUM
Subject Matter	Authentication System
Requirement Sentence	The authentication system SHOULD be aligned with current identity standards such as W3C Verifiable Credentials.
Justification	Alignment with standards fosters helps achieve interoperability, which foster adoption.
Author	UMU
Responsible Task(s)	Task 2.1
Refers to	TANGO D2.3: https://tango-project.eu/materials/public-deliverables

nfn-011

Aspect	Content
Type	Non-Functional
Category	Security
Liability	SHALL
Priority	MEDIUM
Subject Matter	System
Requirement Sentence	The system SHALL implement advanced security measures to prevent unauthorized modification, access, or deletion of data.
Justification	Ensuring data remains secure by preventing unauthorized changes or access is critical for maintaining integrity and confidentiality.
Author	UMU
Responsible Task(s)	Task 2.1
Refers to	EHDS

nfn-012

Aspect	Content
Type	Non-Functional
Category	Interoperability
Liability	SHALL
Priority	HIGH
Subject Matter	System
Requirement Sentence	The system SHALL BE ABLE TO interoperate with EOSC middleware functionalities.
Justification	Interoperability with EOSC.
Author	FRA
Refers to	EOSC IF

nfn-013

Aspect	Content
Type	Non-Functional
Category	Interoperability
Liability	SHALL
Priority	HIGH
Subject Matter	System
Requirement Sentence	The system SHALL BE ABLE TO interoperate with existing data space solutions.
Justification	Interoperability with EOSC.
Author	FRA
Refers to	EOSC IF

nfn-014

Aspect	Content
Type	Non-Functional
Category	Automation
Liability	SHALL
Priority	HIGH
Subject Matter	System
Requirement Sentence	Artefacts used by the system SHALL BE DESIGNED IN A human and machine-readable WAY.
Justification	Machine readability is a standard practice to enable automation of processes.
Author	FRA
Refers to	N/A

nfn-015

Aspect	Content
Type	Non-Functional
Category	Authentication & Authorization
Liability	SHOULD
Priority	MEDIUM
Subject Matter	Data Sharing Platform
Requirement Sentence	The Data Sharing Platform SHOULD BE ABLE TO federate the authentication.
Justification	This enables all external systems to maintain their level of autonomy, there should not be a single centralised authentication method implemented.
Author	FRA
Refers to	GAIA-X

nfn-016

Aspect	Content
Type	Non-Functional
Category	Authentication & Authorization
Liability	SHOULD
Priority	MEDIUM
Subject Matter	Data Sharing Platform
Requirement Sentence	The Data Sharing Platform SHOULD BE ABLE TO support trusted identity providers (eIDAS, edu, ORCID).
Justification	To support standardization and interoperability.
Author	FRA
Refers to	GAIA-X

nfn-017

Aspect	Content
Type	Non-Functional
Category	Security & Privacy
Liability	SHALL
Priority	HIGH
Subject Matter	Data Sharing Platform
Requirement Sentence	The Data Sharing Platform SHALL provide data sovereignty for data owners.
Justification	Data sovereignty is a key concept of data spaces.
Author	FRA
Refers to	GAIA-X, IDSA, DSSC

nfn-018

Aspect	Content
Type	Non-Functional
Category	Security & Privacy
Liability	SHALL
Priority	HIGH
Subject Matter	Data Sharing Platform
Requirement Sentence	The Data Sharing Platform SHALL encrypt data in transit with a secure algorithm suite.
Justification	Exact encryption algorithm shall be defined as soon as the technology is better described.
Author	FRA
Refers to	GDPR, GAIA-X, IDSA, DSSC

nfn-019

Aspect	Content
Type	Non-Functional
Category	Security & Privacy
Liability	SHALL
Priority	HIGH
Subject Matter	Audit System
Requirement Sentence	The Audit System SHALL encrypt data collected and stored for auditing and monitoring purposes to an agreed security strength.
Justification	Exact security requirements shall be defined as soon as the technology is better described.
Author	FRA
Refers to	N/A

nfn-020

Aspect	Content
Type	Non-Functional
Category	Federated Learning
Liability	SHOULD
Priority	MEDIUM
Subject Matter	Federated Learning Toolbox
Requirement Sentence	The Federated Learning Toolbox SHOULD be as agnostic as possible of the executed algorithms and workload code it is to orchestrate.
Justification	Important feature for confidential computing.
Author	ZEN
Responsible Task(s)	T5.1
Refers to	GDPR

nfn-021

Aspect	Content
Type	Non-Functional
Category	Performance & Sustainability
Liability	SHOULD
Priority	HIGH
Subject Matter	Federated Learning Toolbox
Requirement Sentence	The Federated Learning Toolbox performance in orchestrated execution SHOULD be maximally up to one order of magnitude (<10 times) lower compared to referent non-federated execution of the same learning logic/algorithms.
Justification	Key performance and resulting sustainability and cost parameter for the FL toolbox/subsystem (relevant for the Project KPI 3.4). The referent performance metrics should be the main commonly adopted (processing/response time, and/or key throughput/latency...)
Author	ZEN
Responsible Task(s)	T5.1, T5.2
Refers to	EOSC IF

nfn-022

Aspect	Content
Type	Non-Functional
Category	Security & Privacy
Liability	SHALL
Priority	MEDIUM
Subject Matter	Audit System
Requirement Sentence	The Audit System SHALL BE ABLE to carry out the management of control and access privileges.
Justification	Protect sensitive information, prevent unauthorized access, and ensure compliance with security policies and regulations.
Author	FUJ
Responsible Task(s)	Task 2.1
Refers to	NIST CSF (ID, AM-5)

nfn-023

Aspect	Content
Type	Non-Functional
Category	Security & Privacy
Liability	SHALL
Priority	MEDIUM
Subject Matter	Audit System
Requirement Sentence	The Audit System SHALL not contain personal information in logs.
Justification	Logs shall not contain personal information to protect user privacy, comply with data protection regulations, and minimize the risk of exposing sensitive data
Author	FUJ
Responsible Task(s)	Task 2.1
Refers to	GDPR (Article 5);NIST CSF PR,DS-8

nfn-024

Aspect	Content
Type	Non-Functional
Category	Security & Privacy
Liability	SHALL
Priority	MEDIUM
Subject Matter	Audit System
Requirement Sentence	The Audit System SHALL BE ABLE to ensure that log files are append-only.
Justification	Log files should be append-only to maintain the integrity of historical records, prevent tampering, and ensure a reliable audit trail for system and application activities.
Author	FUJ
Responsible Task(s)	Task 2.1
Refers to	NIST CSF (PR,DS-6) (DE,CM-3 DE-CM-8)

nfn-025

Aspect	Content
Type	Non-Functional
Category	Network
Liability	SHALL
Priority	MEDIUM
Subject Matter	System
Requirement Sentence	The system SHALL BE ABLE to identify and categorize network resources, applications, and data into distinct security zones.
Justification	This segmentation enhances security by implementing tailored access controls, monitoring, and protection measures for each zone, reducing the risk of unauthorized access and potential breaches.
Author	FUJ
Responsible Task(s)	Task 2.1
Refers to	NIST CSF (ID, AM-2 5) (PR,AC-5) (PR,DS 2 5) (DE,CM-7)

nfn-026

Aspect	Content
Type	Non-Functional
Category	User Interface
Liability	SHALL
Priority	MEDIUM
Subject Matter	Data Agreement Management Platform
Requirement Sentence	The UI of the Data Agreement Management Platform SHALL BE web-based.
Author	FUJ
Responsible Task(s)	Task 2.1
Refers to	GDPR (Article 5(1)(a)) (Article 5(1)(c)) Article 32 Article 25

nfn-027

Aspect	Content
Type	Non-Functional
Category	User Interface
Liability	SHOULD
Priority	MEDIUM
Subject Matter	Data Agreement Management Platform
Requirement Sentence	The UI of the Data Agreement Management Platform SHOULD BE DESIGNED IN A user-friendly WAY.
Author	FUJ
Responsible Task(s)	Task 2.1
Refers to	GDPR (Article 5(1)(a)) (Article 5(1)(c)) Article 32 Article 25

nfn-028

Aspect	Content
Type	Non-Functional
Category	Authentication & Authorization
Liability	SHALL
Priority	MEDIUM
Subject Matter	System
Requirement Sentence	The system SHALL BE ABLE TO ensure control and restriction of participation to only those entities that are authorized.
Author	FUJ
Responsible Task(s)	Task 2.2
Refers to	NIST CSF (PR, AC-1 3) (PR, ID-2)

nfn-029

Aspect	Content
Type	Non-Functional
Category	Authentication & Authorization
Liability	SHALL
Priority	MEDIUM
Subject Matter	System
Requirement Sentence	The system SHALL BE ABLE TO ensure that cryptographic keys and credentials utilized for TITAN operations are stored securely.
Justification	Prevent unauthorized access, maintain confidentiality, and ensure the integrity of cryptographic operations and sensitive data.
Author	FUJ
Responsible Task(s)	Task 2.2
Refers to	NIST CSF (PR, AC-6) (PR,DS-2 -5)

nfn-030

Aspect	Content
Type	Non-Functional
Category	Security & Privacy
Liability	SHALL
Priority	HIGH
Subject Matter	System
Requirement Sentence	The system SHALL BE ABLE TO protect the data at rest, in transit and in use.
Justification	Protection of data throughout its lifecycle is a cornerstone for digital trust and an enabler for digital collaboration.
Author	CAB
Responsible Task(s)	Task 4.2
Source	Security Experts
Comments	N/A
Refers to	N/A

nfn-031

Aspect	Content
Type	Non-Functional
Category	Data Sharing
Liability	SHOULD
Priority	-
Subject Matter	Metadata Catalog
Requirement Sentence	The Metadata Catalog SHOULD require metadata to use a formal, accessible, shared, and broadly applicable language for knowledge representation.
Justification	FAIR Interoperability
Author	TRI
Refers to	FAIR I1

nfn-032

Aspect	Content
Type	Non-Functional
Category	Data Quality
Liability	SHOULD
Priority	-
Subject Matter	Metadata Catalog
Requirement Sentence	The Metadata Catalog SHOULD require metadata to use vocabularies that follow the FAIR principles.
Justification	FAIR Interoperability
Author	TRI
Refers to	FAIR I2

nfn-033

Aspect	Content
Type	Non-Functional
Category	Data Sharing
Liability	SHOULD
Priority	-
Subject Matter	Metadata Catalog
Requirement Sentence	IF applicable, the Metadata Catalog SHOULD BE ABLE TO include qualified references to other metadata.
Justification	FAIR Interoperability - relevant if data are related or one builds on another
Author	TRI
Refers to	FAIR I3

nfn-034

Aspect	Content
Type	Non-Functional
Category	Data Sharing
Liability	SHOULD
Priority	-
Subject Matter	Metadata Catalog
Requirement Sentence	The Metadata Catalog SHOULD BE ABLE TO associate metadata with detailed provenance.
Justification	FAIR Reusability
Author	TRI
Refers to	FAIR R1.2

nfn-035

Aspect	Content
Type	Non-Functional
Category	Interoperability
Liability	SHOULD
Priority	-
Subject Matter	Metadata Catalog
Requirement Sentence	The Metadata Catalog SHOULD meet domain-relevant community standards.
Justification	FAIR Reusability
Author	TRI
Refers to	FAIR R1.3